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**An automated pipeline for ingesting
bibliographic metadata and citation data into
OpenCitations collections**

Master's thesis

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Abstract

This thesis presents the design, implementation and evaluation of an automated workflow for the preparation, validation and generation of bibliographic metadata and citation data using the OpenCitations software stack. The workflow orchestrates a series of existing OpenCitations tools for the creation of Meta and Index, the two main OpenCitations databases, by integrating data preprocessing, validation, database management and output generation into a single, reproducible pipeline. The proposed solution is implemented in Python using the Luigi workflow management framework, which enables explicit modelling of task dependencies, failure recovery and incremental execution. The workflow coordinates multiple external components, including Redis, OpenLink Virtuoso and RDF triplestores deployed via Docker. Configuration validation and normalisation are performed at runtime to ensure compatibility with the invoked tools and to prevent invalid executions early in the process.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This thesis combines a study of the OpenCitations data model, software stack, and related literature with the design and implementation of an automated workflow that orchestrates the end-to-end process of metadata and citation data generation. The proposed solution integrates preprocessing, validation, database management, and output generation into a single, reproducible pipeline, providing a structured and repeatable way to execute existing OpenCitations tools while reducing manual intervention and configuration errors.

Scholarly citations form one of the simplest, yet most fundamental kinds of bibliographic metadata: each citation creates a directional link from a citing work to a cited one, signalling the author’s debt to earlier research and weaving individual publications into a wider scholarly conversation. Citation relationships underpin bibliometric and scientometric analyses, “they provide insights into the conditions underlying the creativity and the genesis of scientific discovery”, they can be used to trace the evolution of science, and they can help with developing policy for creating and furthering scientific achievements [Fortunato, et al. 2018]. As such, broad, unrestricted access to citation data is essential. Clarivate Analytics’ Web of Science and Elsevier’s Scopus, which are the two largest commercial databases, remain closed and require costly subscriptions that many institutions and virtually all independent researchers cannot afford. OpenCitations was founded to address this barrier by offering a completely free, open, and Linked-Data-compatible corpus of global citation information [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

The existing software stack of OpenCitations provides necessary tools to generate and maintain its core datasets - Meta and Index. However, their practical use requires the careful coordination of multiple independent components. The generation of Meta [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024] and Index [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024] involves a sequence of preprocessing, validation, database initialisation and data loading, as well as exporting and dumping data from databases. Each of these steps relies on specific configuration parameters and external services, such as Redis, RDF triplestores, and OpenLink Virtuoso. When executed manually, this becomes very time-consuming and fragile - configuration errors may only become apparent after long-running steps have completed, partial failures can leave databases in inconsistent states, and reproducing an execution requires precise reconstruction

of the original environment and parameters. As a result, the lack of an integrated execution workflow represents a significant practical barrier, particularly if the users are not directly involved in the development of OpenCitations tools. Automation is therefore needed to coordinate the existing components, but to coordinate them in a controlled and reproducible manner, ensuring that execution logic, dependencies and runtime checks are handled consistently across runs.

The primary aim of this dissertation is to develop an automatization of the current method of creating the two databases of OpenCitations. Before starting the work on automatization, there is a need to research the potential tools available for its' implementation. Regardless of the final choice, a safe assumption may be made that any code will be written in Python for several reasons. Firstly, the bulk of the OpenCitations code is written in Python, and keeping in-line with this would make it easier to maintain this part of the functionality for the other members of the group. Python is also positioned as both a popular and high-level language for general use, therefore making it a good choice for the implementation. The vast collection of Python libraries may also reduce development time.

The following objectives should cover all necessary activities to fulfil the primary aim of the dissertation:

1. Research OpenCitations

Conducting research on OpenCitations to gain understanding on the system that will be automatised. This includes the preprocessing (extracting citations and metadata), OpenCitations Meta (curation of metadata, allocation of identifiers, metadata and provenance of data production), and OpenCitations Index (conversion of citations, production of citation and provenance data).

2. Research other attempts at developing open bibliographic data

Conducting research on related works, i.e. other existing attempts at developing open-source bibliographic citation projects, such as (but possibly not limited to) OpenAIRE, OpenAlex and WikiCite. The goal of this objective is to provide a deeper look and understanding of the open science community and the need to provide free options for providing data relating to bibliographic citations.

3. Research potential tools

Conducting research on tools that may be used for the implementation of the automatization process of OpenCitations. While the main aim of the project is to provide a process that will be compliant with a open-source licence, such as BSD, ISC or MIT; additional methods will be looked into as well, to provide a more “state-of-the-art” approach if applicable.

4. Implement the automatization

Developing the automatization process of creating the OpenCitations database.

5. Evaluate the automatization

Evaluating the accomplishment of user requirements, running the automatization of the workflow locally (i.e. on my personal computer), then using the automatization as a part of the regular workflow of developing an update for the OpenCitations data sets.

The dissertation will be structured in the following manner:

- Chapter 2: Literature review – Brief introduction and analysis of open bibliographic data projects related to OpenCitations, including their data ingestion methods; research of literature for OpenCitations, the potential concepts it is based upon, carried out to gain understanding on the project that will be worked on; brief examination of frameworks for creating automated data processing pipelines.
- Chapter 3: Methodology – Outlining the technology used for the development of the application, use case scenarios and descriptions, user requirements, MoSCoW analysis of the requirements, project management: project plans, risk identification, analysis, and mitigation plans, PLES issues; selection of the framework for creating automated data processing pipelines.
- Chapter 4: Implementation – Outlining work carried out with the implementation of the project.
- Chapter 5: Evaluation – Evaluation of the fulfilment of the requirements and the resulting outcome of the automatization process; evaluation of risk planning analysis.
- Chapter 6: Conclusion – Summarising the project, limitations and possible extensions to the project, analysis of aims and objectives.

Chapter 2

Literature review

2.1 Related works

In this section, a selection of open research information (“information that is free to access and free of restrictions on reuse”, as per the *Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information* [Barcelona, 2024]) providers producing openly available datasets with scholarly bibliographic metadata will be reviewed. All numbers provided here have been checked in July 2025.

2.1.1 WikiCite

WikiData was introduced in 2012 as an open knowledge base to store data from other Wikimedia projects (e.g. Wikipedia, Wiktionary, etc.) in an RDF format. Stemming from Wikidata, WikiCite was officially started in 2016 as an internal community working on bibliographical information [Taraborelli, 2016]. WikiCite currently contains information on 45,164,215 scholarly articles [Scholia, 2025]. Data is released under a CC0 licence as JSON, XML and RDF dumps [WikiData, 2025a]. Users can browse the dataset using SPARQL, a web interface and using the Scholia web service providing statistics and valuable infographics. Data ingestion for WikiCite and Wikidata in general works in the same general way; the datasets selected for import are first imported into a spreadsheet, then the structure of data in Wikidata is defined, afterwards the imported data is formatted, matched and added, before checking the results and summarising the import [WikiData, 2025b]. Data is added manually, either on the Wikidata website, or more often using tools assisting with metadata entry and curation, like Wikidata Edit Framework; there are also bots that import the curated data to Wikidata [WikiData, 2025c].

2.1.2 SciGraph

Springer Nature’s SciGraph [Hammond, Pasin, Theodoridis, 2017] was an aggregator of data from Springer Nature and its partners. It contained entities concerning publications, affiliations, conferences, funders and research projects, totalling more than 14 million products and 2 billion triples. A public SPARQL endpoint was never released, but the data was browsable using a web interface, and dumps were

released monthly under CC-BY licence [Massari, Mariani, Heibi, Peroni, Shotton, 2024]. SciGraph was officially discontinued at the beginning of 2023 [Perin, 2023]. The data ingestion pipeline was also never made public.

2.1.3 BioTea

BioTea represents the annotated full-text open-access subset of PubMed using RDF [García, López et al., 2018]. Metadata and citations are described and the annotated full texts are defined semantically. Three datasets have been released; the initial one containing 270,384 articles in July 2012 [BioTea, 2025a], the second one containing 6000 articles in August 2017 [BioTea, 2025b], and the most recent one containing 2,811 articles in February 2019. The latter, in addition to RDF/XML dumps, was also released in JSON-LD and schema.org formats [BioTea, 2025c]. The datasets are released as “open” on Zenobo, therefore an assumption is that they are released under CC0 licence [BioTea, 2012], while the code is available under the Apache 2.0 licence [BioTea, 2025d]. The data ingestion starts with batch processing of JATS-XML (Journal Articles Suite) files containing PubMed Central-Open Access articles, extracting PMC identifiers, titles, abstracts, authors, references, sections, paragraphs and text; paragraph fragments are then semantically enriched using a named entity recognition service from NCBO Annotator, part of BioPortal. [BioTea, 2025e].

2.1.4 Open Research Knowledge Graph

The Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) differs somewhat from the rest of the other works described in this section, as it is primarily focused not on the bibliographic metadata, but rather on describing research papers in a structured manner, allowing for similarity analysis [Auer, Oelen et al., 2020]. As such, while ORKG does use automatically collected metadata from Crossref, the annotations provided on topic, method, result and context are done by hand for each resource. The dataset consists of 34 thousands papers, 1,200 comparisons, 343 visualisations, 45 reviews and 10 lists [ORKG, 2025a]. The data is accessible through a web-based search tool, a REST API, a Python package wrapping the API, a SPARQL endpoint and a RDF dump [ORKG, 2025b]. The code of ORKG is made available under the MIT licence, and the data is published under the CC0 licence, with the exception of the data coming from one specified source under the CC-BY-SA licence [ORKG, 2025c]. The data ingestion is done either programmatically via the aforementioned API, or by hand using one of several structured templates, including a PDF annotator, bulk import from a CSV file or a grid editor [ORKG, 2025d].

2.1.5 Open Ukrainian Scientific Content Initiative

The Open Ukrainian Scientific Content Initiative (OUCI) of the State Science and Technical Library of Ukraine is a web-based search engine and citation database tool, that contains information on 171 million publications, 1,950 Ukrainian journals from

383 publishers and 705,329 publications in Ukrainian journals, which use the Crossref Cited-by service and support the Initiative for Open Citations [OUCI, 2025]. The primary aim of the project is to enhance access to scholarly citation data, especially by improving the level of bibliometrics studies at the national level [Franchuk, 2023]. No information is given regarding the licence for either code, or the data provided by the service. The data ingestion method is likewise not directly specified except for using Crossref’s REST API. Because of that, we can infer that it is mostly automatic, as OUCI is mostly based on Crossref metadata, with additional metadata enrichment in the form of Web of Science/Scopus indexation, Ukrainian journal category and categorisation of the field of knowledge according to the Ukrainian legislation.

2.1.6 iCite

iCite is a web-based database tool provided by the U.S. Department of Health & Human Services’ National Institutes of Health’s Division of Program Coordination, Planning and Strategic Initiatives. It allows for access to citation data for 33,045,463 publications available on PubMed. iCite provides a web interface, in which a user can search PubMed, paste a list of PubMed Identifiers (PMIDs), or upload a spreadsheet of PMIDs to receive the bibliometrics for the specified articles [iCite, 2025a]. Searches are routed through the Entrez service of National Library of Medicine, so they may provide different search results compared to ones made directly on PubMed, especially if PMIDs cannot be matched [iCite, 2025b]. Additionally, it is possible to download the data in bulk via monthly snapshots, which is distributed under CC0 licence [iCite, 2019]. iCite’s data ingestion pipeline is not open, but it is known that the data is pulled from the authoritative bibliographic databases on National Institute of Health. [Heibi, 2024].

2.1.7 Semantic Scholar

Semantic Scholar was launched in 2015 by the Allen Institute for Artificial Intelligence [Fricke, 2018]. The database of Semantic Scholar currently contains 227,599,898 academic papers [Semantic Scholar, 2025a]. Semantic Scholar’s main database is the Semantic Scholar Academic Graph, access to which is available via a RESTful API. Semantic Scholar provides a general-purpose API key, limited to shared 1000 requests per second, however one can request a private key with its’ own limit of 1 request per second [Semantic Scholar, 2025b]. Additionally, the data can be accessed via a web interface. The licence for the Semantic Scholar is proprietary, however the data accessed from the service is “separately governed by the licenses that accompany such data, such as CC-BY-NC or ODC-BY” [Semantic Scholar, 2025c]. Semantic Scholar has a sophisticated data processing pipeline, that starts with ingesting documents and metadata from “more than 50 input sources”, including Crossref, arXiv and the Allen Institute’s web crawler. The structured metadata is then augmented with normalised information from the papers’ PDF publications; this is done by extracting text, annotating visual regions of the documents, and annotating text spans by giving semantic labels to extracted tokens. Before constructing the knowledge graph, permanent identifiers are given to papers, citations,

publication venues, authors and author affiliations, which are thus normalised, deduplicated and disambiguated [Kinney, 2025].

2.1.8 ScholarlyData

ScholarlyData collects only the information about conferences and workshops that were held on the topic of the Semantic Web [Nuzzolese, Gentile et al., 2016]. Data is modelled following the conference-ontology, describing entities that are typical for a scholarly conference, e.g. accepted papers, authors and their affiliations, but not bibliographical references. The database currently stores information on 5507 papers. Data is available via a SPARQL endpoint and RDF dumps of linked datasets. The external links to ScholarlyData datasets are not active. [ScholarlyData, 2025]. The data ingestion of ScholarlyData uses an in-house tool cLODg. [Gentile, 2016] cLODg accepts any RDF conference metadata represented with the SWC ontology, CSV files exported from EasyChair; or describing keynote talks, organising committees, sessions, talks and special events, or XML files exported from EasyChair. This data is then converted into the Conference Ontology; CSV data first requires a manual import into a MySQL database. [cLODg, 2016].

2.1.9 OpenAIRE Graph

OpenAIRE is a non-profit organisation funded to promote open scholarship and enhance data accessibility, shareability, discoverability, reproducibility and reusability [Manghi, Manola et al., 2010]. The most relevant part of the OpenAIRE project is the OpenAIRE Graph, which indexes over 290 million works from 140 thousand data sources, which are linked to 4 million projects, grants, organisations and communities with over 7 billion relations [Manghi et al., 2022]. OpenAIRE provides numerous APIs to access the data, as well as the extensive search subpage called Explore and the ability to download the entire dataset, sub-graph datasets and other related datasets [OpenAIRE, 2025a] [OpenAIRE, 2025b]. The data is provided under CC-BY licence due to the licensing of some of its data sources, however, parts of the database is said to be published under CC0 licence (although it is not specified which parts exactly) [OpenAIRE, 2025c]. The current core sources and repositories OpenAIRE lists are DOAJ, Crossref, Unpaywall, ORCID, Microsoft Academic Graph, Datacite, UKPubMed, arXiv, HAL, Zenodo, Figshare, Dryad and Repec [OpenAIRE, 2025d]. The documentation for the data ingestion process is incomplete, however it contains enough to provide some basic information; the metadata is harvested in an automatised way, aggregating it from around 10000 trusted sources. the data is aggregated by major sources, then deduplicated and enriched using text-mining, deduction-based inference and propagation [OpenAIRE, 2025e].

2.1.10 OpenAlex

OpenAlex [Priem, Piwowar, Orr, 2022] is a direct continuation of the Microsoft Academic Graph [Sinha, Shen et al., 2015], the discontinuation of which was seen

as problematic due to the issues with replacing it on existing systems [Tay, Martín-Martín, Hug, 2021]. OpenAlex indexes over 250 million works from around 250 thousand sources, and claims to put extra care on humanities, Global South and works written in languages other than English. These works are linked to circa 90 million authors and 100 thousand institutions, with additional linking to topic information, SDGs, citation counts, etc. The data can be accessed via a search function on the project website, via an API, or via downloading the entire OpenAlex dataset [OpenAlex, 2025a]. The data is provided under the CC0 licence, however, OpenAlex currently operates under a freemium revenue model, with limits on update frequency and API being put on non-paying users [OpenAlex, 2025b]. This model is a likely reason for OpenAlex' data ingestion pipeline for being not open, and only residual information being provided. The current core sources OpenAlex lists are CrossRef, DataCite, PubMed, HAL, DOAJ, ORCID, MAG, arXiv, Dergipark, OSTI, RePEc, UNC Carolina, University of Michigan Deep Blue, Zenodo and ISSN [OpenAlex, 2025c]. Data is sourced from MAG, Crossref, DataCite, etc., the affiliations and citations between papers are found, and "aboutness", that is, keywords and topics are tagged [OpenAlex, 2025d]. Despite the closedness of the data ingestion pipeline, the metrics are made available online [OpenAlex, 2025e].

2.2 OpenCitations

2.2.1 Introduction

In this section, the organisation of OpenCitations will be introduced, followed by an analysis of some of the tools that it has produced, as well as the existing workflow of creating the published datasets. This will be done in order to gain comprehension of what is meant to be developed as the practical part of the dissertation.

OpenCitations is an infrastructure organisation centred in the Faculty of Classic Literature and Italian Studies at the University of Bologna for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open citation data as Linked Open Data using Semantic Web technologies, providing an alternative to traditional proprietary citation indexes. Open citation data are valuable for bibliometric analyses, as they are increasing the reproducibility of large-scale analyses by enabling the publication of the source data [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

The first data set containing open bibliographic and citation data was OpenCitations Corpus, which was released in in 2010, being made as a part of the Open Citations Project, which was being funded at the time by a UK government-funded organisation called Joint Information Systems Committee. However, this initial version was of limited scope. Following the release of Open Citations Corpus, there was a small number of reference lists, that had been made openly available by Crossref until early 2017. In April 2017, Initiative for Open Citations was launched, of which OpenCitations is one of the founding members [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

Initiative for Open Citations was funded with the intention of promoting the release of citation data openly, by asking scholarly publishers to make them open for everyone. This data, consisting of reference lists was already being deposited on Crossref. After first two years of operation of the Initiative, the percentage of papers with open references on Crossref has risen from 1% to 59%. Crossref currently provides fully open metadata of over 160 million records [Crossref, 2025].

[Peroni, Shotton, 2020] characterises the development of the open scholarship movement in the following four phases:

- Open-source software; such as Linux-based operating systems,
- Open-access publications and open-access publishers; such as PLoS, eLife and F1000 Research,
- Open-research data sets; such as Protein Databank and Dryad Data Repository,
- Open bibliographic metadata; such as PubMed and Crossref.

Additionally, [Peroni, Shotton, 2020] provides following benefacting reasons for the existence of an open bibliographic citation system:

- Researchers and authors than cannot afford subscription access to commercial citation indexes, e.g. WoS, can use the open-source alternative free of charge,
- Bibliometricians are able to publish their research findings alongside the research data it was based on,

- Librarians can better support their communities by providing free access to citations,
- Funders can better access the impact of scientific work,
- Academic administrators can track scholarly productivity and influence more easily,
- Research managers can integrate the data in their CRIS systems,
- Data repositories can benefit from citations between their data sets and articles describing them,
- Publishers of online journals have more readers guided to them, which will also attract additional article submissions,
- Computer scientists and software developers can build new applications and visualisations with the new data.

This shift of open scholarship towards data provision brings an additional technological aspect, namely developing an infrastructure, which would be able to store and serve all bibliographic data of interest, with a potential for scalability in the future. The main problem lies with the impossibility of centralisation of this information in a single solution, as the amount of data and managing the service would require too much resources. As such, it does seem that, among the options for the development of this distributed scholarly infrastructure, Semantic Web technologies provide one of the most appropriate solutions [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

2.2.2 Current workflow

The workflow for making bibliographic metadata and citation data from external sources OCDM-compliant and ingesting it into OpenCitations' collections involves three steps [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024]:

1. Source Preprocess: In this step, the data is reshaped through a metadata crosswalk, converting the various data models from the original sources to the OCDM format, while addressing differences in information content, structure, and representation. A key operation is the normalization and validation of external PIDs, such as DOIs for publications and ORCIDs for authors and editors. The output of this phase, produced by the OpenCitations Data Sources Converter, consists of two OCDM-compliant tables. One stores bibliographic metadata for each publication involved in a citation, with each row representing a publication and columns containing values for supported metadata fields. The second table stores citations, with each row representing a citation and two columns storing the PIDs of the citing and cited publications, following the citation schema of the original source (e.g., DOI-to-DOI citations from Crossref).

Figure 2.1: Diagram showing the current workflow of OpenCitations. Red box encompasses the current automatization needs.

2. Meta Process: This step populates the OpenCitations Meta collection. Starting with the table produced in the Source Preprocess phase, the bibliographic metadata is automatically curated by deduplicating records with identical PIDs and normalizing or correcting their values. Records representing entities previously registered in OpenCitations Meta can be used to enrich existing metadata or merge separate entities (if the external PIDs, though appearing to belong to a single entity in the record, actually reference distinct entities in OpenCitations Meta). Each entity in OpenCitations Meta is assigned a unique OpenCitations Meta Identifier (OMID) upon its creation, which is essential for identifying publications linked by citations without relying on external identifiers. The output of this phase, detailed in another section, is the OpenCitations Meta dataset, stored both in a database and as dump files. Additionally, provenance information is generated and stored in RDF files, tracking the agent responsible for creating, modifying, merging, or deleting

each entity, the time of the action, and the primary data source.

3. **Index Process:** In this final step, the citation tables from the Source Preprocess phase are processed, with each citation representing a link between two external PIDs (e.g., DOI-to-DOI, PMID-to-PMID). Using a mapping between these external identifiers and the OMIDs assigned to the entities in the Meta Process step, the citations are converted into OMID-to-OMID citations, each uniquely identified by an Open Citation Identifier. The output of this step is the OpenCitations Index dataset, with citation data stored in a database and as dump files, and provenance information saved in RDF files.

The workflow outlined above is currently applied only to data from authoritative sources, such as Crossref or DataCite, which structure their data according to a defined model. While this workflow is highly beneficial - especially for integrating large volumes of data with each execution - its use is limited to data sources where implementing a metadata crosswalk from the source data model to OCDM is both feasible and advantageous. Given the significant effort required to manage the complexities of each source, creating custom data conversions for every source may not be a viable approach, particularly for sources that lack key conditions to facilitate this process (e.g., a well-defined data model or clear documentation of the data structure). [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025]

2.2.3 OpenCitations tools and services

This subsection will introduce relevant tools and services made by OpenCitations.

OpenCitations Identifiers

OpenCitations Identifiers (OCI) are globally unique permanent identifiers used for open bibliographic citation. The OCI system has been developed, as its name suggests, by OpenCitations, which also maintains a resolution service for these identifiers. The resolution service retrieves metadata about the citation identified by a valid OCI in RDF, Scholix, JSON or CSV [Peroni, Shotton, 2018].

OCIs are strings of characters beginning with lowercase “oci”, a colon and two numerical sequences separated by a dash. The first sequence identifies the citing publication and the supplier database of the metadata. The second sequence identifies the cited publication and its supplier database of the metadata. Each supplier database is defined by a numerical prefix containing a short sequence of digits delimited by zeroes. This means that alphanumeric identifiers like DOI are transformed into purely numeric sequences. OCIs were primarily designed with machine processing instead of human readability in mind, so the length of the strings created by the transformation does not form problems [Peroni, Shotton, 2019].

OCIs encode directional relationships between identified citing and cited entities, the provenance of the citation and the type of identifiers used in the provenance database, and as such, they are not opaque identifiers, containing all information necessary to construct a citation network [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

OpenCitations Data Model and Ontology

OpenCitations has initially developed the OpenCitations Data Model in 2016 to describe the data in the OpenCitations Corpus. Since OpenCitations has moved on to develop other data sets, and OCDM was adopted for use by external projects, such as the Open Biomedical Citations in Context Corpus, the OCDM has been expanded further to accommodate these changes. OCDM allows for recording metadata about bibliographic references and their textual contexts, bibliographic entities (i.e. citing and cited works) and the citations linking them, agents and their roles (e.g. author), identifiers for the entities, and more [Daquino, Peroni et al., 2020].

Terms that are described in OCDM are brought together in the OpenCitations Ontology, which also includes terms from well-know ontologies, such as SPAR, PROV-O and Web Annotation Ontology. In OCO [Daquino, Peroni et al., 2020]:

- Citations are instances of the class *cito:Citation*, as defined in the Citation Typing Ontology. It's subclasses include e.g. *cito:JournalSelfCitation* and *cito:AuthorNetworkSelfCitation*. Additionally, citations can be characterised with a purpose or function with respect to the related citation context by means of CiTO properties, such as *cito:hasCitationCharacterisation*.
- Bibliographic metadata such as publication dates, authors and venues can be linked to instances of the class *fabio:Expression*, as defined in the FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology.
- Specific editions and formats are aggregated in the instances of *fabio:Manifestation*.
- Instances of the class *cito:Citation* are linked using instances of *oa:Annotation*, as defined in the Web Annotation Ontology, to instances of *biro:BibliographicReference* (defined in the Bibliographic Reference Ontology) and individuals of *c4o:InTextReferencePointer* (defined in the Citation Counting and Context Characterisation Ontology),
- Lists of in-text reference pointers are represented by the class *c4o:SingleLocationPointerList*.
- Structural elements, in which such in-text reference pointers appear are represented as individuals of the class *deo:DiscourseElement*, as defined in the Discourse Element Ontology.
- Elements are uniquely identified by instances of the class *datacite:Identifier*, as defined in the DataCite Ontology.

OCDM also provides guidance for describing the versioning and provenance of each entity under consideration and enables the specification of main metadata related to data sets containing such entities, by re-using terms from PROV-O, VOID and DCAT. Each bibliographic entity described by OCDM is annotated with one or more provenance snapshots (instances of *prov:Entity*). Each snapshot records a set of statements having the bibliographic entity as the subject at a fixed point

Figure 2.2: Main classes and properties of the OpenCitations Ontology.

in time, validity dates, agents responsible for creation or modification of the meta-data, primary data sources and a SPARQL query summarising changes with respect to prior snapshots. A dataset (instance of *dcate:Dataset*) containing information about the bibliographic entities is described with information (such as title, description, publication dates, SPARQL endpoint) and distribution information (instance of *dcate:Distribution*), which includes the specification of licences, dumps, media types and data volumes [Daquino, Peroni et al., 2020].

Figure 2.3: Provenance, versioning and dataset description in the OCDM.

OpenCitations collections

The first collection developed by OpenCitations was the OpenCitation Corpus, a database of downloadable open citation and bibliographic data recorded in RDF and release under a Creative Commons CC0 licence, containing information about around 14 million citation links and over 7 million cited resources [Peroni, Shotton, Vitali, 2017].

Currently, OpenCitations provides data in two collections. OpenCitations Index [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024] provides OMID-to-OMID references representing all citations from multiple sources. As of July 2025, Index includes data on over 2.2 billion citations, available via SPARQL queries, API calls or dumps in CSV, N-triple or Scholix formats under the CC0 licence. OpenCitations Meta [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024] provides bibliographic metadata for all publications in the OpenCitations Index, which includes data on over 120 million bibliographic entities, over 375 million authors and over 1 million publication venues. OpenCitations Meta is available via SPARQL queries, API calls and dumps in CSV and Kubernetes Ready formats under the CC0 licence [OpenCitations, 2025]. Both Index and Meta, as well as the process of their creation are analysed in further detail in other sections of the dissertation.

Provenance information

The provenance of a resource concerns “the people, institutions, entities and activities involved in producing, influencing or delivering a piece of data or a thing” and “is crucial in deciding whether information is to be trusted, how it should be integrated with other diverse information sources, and how to give credit to its originators when reusing it” [Moreau, Missier, 2013]. Both OpenCitations data sets also have corresponding provenance databases available to download via dumps (CSV and N-triple formats for Index, RDF for Meta) [OpenCitations, 2025]. All the entities are accompanied by provenance information to keep track of the curatorial activities related to each entity, the curatorial agents involved and the sources that were used to obtain the data, as well as tracking how the data related to the entities may have changed in time [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

OpenCitations software

Aforementioned data is made available in RDF, the main format for expressing structured machine-readable data for the web, and is stored in triple-stores. OpenCitations provides open-source software of generic applicability of searching, browsing and querying its bibliographic and citation data on GitHub

(<https://github.com/opencitations>). Programmatic access to the triple-stores may be obtained via SPARQL queries, via REST API using OpenCitations RAMOSE, via creating REST APIs over SPARQL endpoints using OpenCitations COCI or via HTTP requests. The datasets can also be explored using OSCAR by inputting an identifier, title or author name, and then browsed using LUCINDA. The entire data sets are available to download as dumps hosted on Zenodo, Figshare and Internet Archive [Peroni, Shotton, 2020].

Validator and monitor

This subsection examines two complementary OpenCitations tools, *oc_validator* and *oc_monitor*, which address data quality at different stages of the ingestion lifecycle. While the validator focuses on detecting issues before data are incorporated into the OpenCitations datasets, the monitor operates after ingestion to continuously assess the integrity of the published collections. Together, these tools form a two-layer quality assurance strategy that combines preventive checks with ongoing supervision.

A key motivation for these tools is the increasing availability of bibliographic metadata produced outside controlled institutional pipelines. Although many organisations and researchers possess valuable citation data, these resources are often difficult to integrate due to heterogeneous formats and varying levels of standardisation. Enabling external contributions — for example through crowdsourced submissions — requires mechanisms that guarantee consistency with the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM). Consequently, automated validation becomes essential to prevent malformed or inconsistent records from degrading the quality of the core datasets [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

Pre-ingestion validation To lower the technical barrier for contributors, OpenCitations adopts a tabular CSV-based format for submissions. This format is accessible to non-programmers while still capable of expressing the structured information required by OCDM. Two specialised table types are defined: META-CSV for bibliographic metadata and CITS-CSV for citation relationships [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

META-CSV tables describe individual bibliographic entities and include fields such as identifiers, titles, authors and editors, publication information, and venue details. In contrast, CITS-CSV files are intentionally simpler and represent citation links between resources using a smaller number of columns. Despite this apparent simplicity, both formats allow cells to contain multiple values separated by delimiters, meaning that each cell may encode several logical data items. In some cases, these items may themselves be internally structured, for example combining names with persistent identifiers. This nested structure increases the complexity of validation [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

To address this, validation rules are grouped into several categories, including checks for syntactic correctness, compliance with external identifier standards, con-

firmation of the existence of referenced entities, and verification of logical consistency between related values. The validator applies these rules systematically to every item extracted from each table cell [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

An important design requirement of the validator is that its output must serve both automated systems and human users. Validation results are therefore generated in a structured, machine-readable form that can be integrated into processing pipelines, while also providing clear and descriptive feedback to help contributors understand and correct errors. Reports include detailed information such as the location of problematic entries, the type of rule violated, and explanatory messages. This dual-format reporting approach supports both programmatic filtering of invalid records and manual debugging of submissions [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

Post-ingestion data quality assurance Even rigorous pre-ingestion checks cannot guarantee that all inconsistencies are eliminated. Errors may emerge later due to evolving datasets, integration issues, or previously undetected anomalies. For this reason, OpenCitations complements validation with continuous monitoring [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

The monitoring component, *oc_monitor*, periodically inspects the contents of OpenCitations Meta and OpenCitations Index to detect known classes of problems. Rather than validating individual submissions, it evaluates the datasets as a whole. The tool relies on a catalogue of recognised error patterns, each formally described and associated with a method for automated detection [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

Many of these checks are implemented as SPARQL queries executed directly against the triplestore endpoints. This strategy allows efficient identification of problematic records without requiring full data exports or external processing. For each monitored condition, the tool records whether matching instances were found and summarises the results in a consolidated report [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

The monitoring process is designed for regular, unattended execution. Tests are performed periodically, and the outcomes are published in both structured and human-readable formats. This enables integration with automated workflows while also providing transparency for users who wish to inspect the health of the datasets manually [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

oc_validator The *oc_validator* tool is implemented in Python and distributed as an open-source package. Its core component is the `Validator` class, which processes a single CSV file at a time and produces validation reports for that document. For workflows that require simultaneous handling of both metadata and citation tables, a lightweight wrapper coordinates multiple validator instances [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

Internally, the validator first determines the type of the input table and then applies the corresponding validation routine. Each cell is parsed according to the semantics of its column, after which a sequence of rule checks is executed. Rules are organised into dedicated classes representing different validation levels, allowing modular extension and maintenance. When a rule fails, dependent checks are skipped to improve efficiency [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

Detected issues are recorded as structured error objects, which are later exported to JSON for machine consumption and to text or HTML formats for human review.

The HTML representation provides an interactive interface in which problematic cells are highlighted and accompanied by explanatory tooltips, facilitating rapid inspection of large tables [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

oc_monitor The monitoring tool follows a similar design philosophy. It is also implemented in Python and configured through external JSON files. Two main components, *MetaMonitor* and *IndexMonitor*, operate on their respective datasets [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

Each configuration specifies the endpoint to query and defines a set of tests, including descriptive metadata and the SPARQL queries required to detect specific error patterns. During execution, the monitor evaluates each test sequentially and records the outcome together with execution details such as runtime and potential connection issues [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

The final results are aggregated into structured reports that can be processed automatically or rendered for human interpretation. Within the OpenCitations infrastructure, the monitoring process is integrated into scheduled automation, ensuring that dataset quality is assessed on a regular basis and that any detected problems are promptly visible [Peroni, Rizzetto, 2025].

2.2.4 OpenCitations Meta

OpenCitations Meta is an open database that provides bibliographic metadata about scholarly publications involved in citations recorded by the OpenCitations infrastructure. Aligned with Open Science principles, its data is openly available under a CC0 license to facilitate extensive reuse. Currently, it integrates metadata from major providers such as Crossref, DataCite, and PubMed, positioning itself as a prominent source of bibliographic metadata leveraging Semantic Web standards. Each resource within OpenCitations Meta receives a unique, globally persistent identifier known as an OpenCitations Meta Identifier (OMID). These OMIDs support disambiguation of resources identified by different external identifiers, e.g. publications referenced by both Crossref DOIs and PubMed PMIDs, and also manage citation data involving resources without external identifiers [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

OpenCitations Meta methodology

OpenCitations Meta is populated using input data in CSV format, a deliberate choice based on the fact that OpenCitations' CSV files are downloaded more often than those in more structured formats like JSON Scholix. The CSV format is preferred for its smaller file size and, crucially, its ease of readability for humans. This accessibility is the primary reason OpenCitations Meta adopts CSV as its input format, as it simplifies the future crowdsourcing of bibliographic metadata through human curatorial activities. The input table for OpenCitations Meta contains 11 columns, reflecting a linearized version of the OCDM: id, title, author, editor, publication date, venue, volume, issue, page, type, and publisher. After the CSV data is obtained, it undergoes an automated curation process before being converted into an RDF-based OCDM format. Both the curated CSV and RDF files are stored,

and the associated triple-store is gradually populated [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Curator - deduplication, enrichment and correction

The curation process focuses on three key actions to improve the quality of the incoming data: deduplication, enrichment, and correction. Notably, the entire process is fully automated, requiring no manual intervention [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

The data deduplication process relies exclusively on identifiers. Two entities are considered identical if, and only if, they share the same identifier, such as a DOI for articles, an ORCID for individuals, an ISBN for books, or an ISSN for publication venues. When multiple identifiers exist for an entity, all of them are taken into account during the deduplication process. If different resources share the same identifier, they are merged based on a specific rule: if the resources come from the same CSV file, the information from the first occurrence is preferred. However, if the resource already exists in the triple-store, the data in the triple-store takes precedence. The information stored in the triple-store is regarded as reliable and can only be enriched with additional data from the CSV source [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

After an entity is deduplicated, it is assigned a permanent internal identifier known as the OpenCitations Meta Identifier (OMID). The OMID follows the format `[entity_type_abbreviation]/[supplier_prefix][sequential_number]`. For instance, the first journal article processed would have the OMID "br/0601," where "br" stands for "bibliographic resource," "060" is the supplier prefix indicating the database the resource belongs to, and "1" signifies that this OMID represents the first bibliographic resource recorded for that supplier prefix in the index [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

The supplier prefix used in OpenCitations Meta follows the pattern "06[1-9]*0," meaning valid prefixes include "060," "0610," and "06230." The decision to use a range of prefixes, instead of just one, is driven by technical considerations related to the system's capacity for parallel processing. By utilizing multiple prefixes, different directories can be processed simultaneously, each assigned a unique name corresponding to a specific supplier prefix. This approach enhances workflow efficiency. Despite the variation in prefixes, they all remain part of the OpenCitations Meta framework. The use of supplier prefixes in OMID identifiers serves multiple purposes. Firstly, it helps identify the source database for provenance tracking, which is crucial for automated metadata processing. For example, the prefix "060" indicates that OpenCitations Meta is the source of the metadata. Secondly, the structure of the prefix, ending in "0," facilitates clear and unambiguous automated parsing. The choice of "06" as the prefix for OpenCitations Meta aligns with the supplier prefixes used for Open Citation Identifiers, ensuring consistency across different types of identifiers within the OpenCitations ecosystem, and reinforcing the robustness and traceability of the metadata [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Entities that undergo deduplication and are assigned an OMID include external identifiers (*id*), agent roles (*ar*), responsible agents (*ra*), resource embodiments (*re*), and bibliographic resources like venues, volumes, and issues (*br*). Volumes and issues

are assigned OMIDs because they are treated as first-class entities, rather than mere attributes of articles. This approach makes it possible to search for papers within a specific issue, volumes of a particular journal, or journal issues published within a given time frame. In contrast, titles and dates are considered literal values, not entities [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Given an input entity and its identifiers, there are six possible outcomes [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024]:

1. If the entity has no identifiers or if the identifiers do not exist in the triple-store, a new OMID is generated for the entity.
2. If the entity does not have an OMID, but one of its external identifiers is already associated with exactly one other entity, the two entities are merged and treated as a single entity.
3. If the entity's external identifiers in the CSV link to two or more previously separate entities in the triple-store, and no OMID is provided in the CSV, a conflict arises that cannot be resolved automatically and will require manual intervention. A new OMID is created for the conflicting entity.
4. If an entity in the CSV has an OMID that already exists in the triple-store and no other identifiers are provided, the information in the triple-store takes precedence, and only the missing details from the CSV are added. Essentially, specifying the OMID in the CSV updates the existing entity in OpenCitations Meta.
5. If an entity has an existing OMID and additional identifiers are linked to other entities (either without an OMID or with the same OMID), those entities are merged. The data from the CSV is then overwritten by the data in the triple-store, and any missing details from the CSV are added to the triple-store.
6. If external identifiers link multiple entities in the triple-store with different OMIDs, a conflict occurs. In this case, the OMID specified in the CSV takes precedence, and only entities with that OMID are merged.

Three specific cases require special attention. The first involves the order of authors and editors, which must be maintained according to the OCDM. During a merge, the order established when the entity was initially created takes precedence, and any new authors or editors are appended to the end of the list. The second case arises when two bibliographic resources are merged and the authors or editors do not have identifiers. In this situation, they are disambiguated based on their given and family names. The third case concerns the containment relationships between articles, issues, volumes, and venues. This structure is preserved during a merge, where two volumes or issues are considered identical only if they share the same value, whether it is a sequential number or an arbitrary name [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Curator - error proofing

Once all entities have been assigned an OMID, the data undergoes normalization, and automatically correctable errors are addressed. Each identifier is validated according to its respective scheme. For instance, the syntactic correctness of ISBNs, ISSNs, and ORCIDs is verified using formulas defined in the identifier scheme documentation. However, semantic correctness is only checked for ORCIDs and DOIs, using open APIs to confirm their actual existence. This step is crucial because, for example, an ORCID might be syntactically valid but not actually assigned to any individual [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

All ambiguous or alternative characters used for spaces are replaced with a standard space. Likewise, ambiguous hyphen characters within IDs, pages, volumes, issues, authors, and editors are converted to a hyphen-minus. For bibliographic resource titles, each word is capitalized, except for those already containing capital letters (which are considered acronyms). This exception does not apply to titles that are fully capitalized. The same rule is applied to authors and editors, whether individuals or organizations. Dates are parsed by validating both the format (following ISO 8601: YYYY-MM-DD) and the actual value. If needed, the date is truncated, and any date with an invalid year is discarded. The correction of volume and issue numbers follows a set of established rules, with six identified error types [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Patterns identified as volumes include terms such as "original series," "volume," "vol," and their equivalents in various languages. Likewise, patterns recognized as issues include terms like "issue," "special issue," and their counterparts in other languages. If a value is both incorrectly formatted and placed in the wrong field, it is first corrected and then moved to the correct field, if applicable. Once the input data has been disambiguated, enriched, and corrected, a new CSV file is generated and saved [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Creator - semantic mapping

In this phase, the data is modeled in RDF based on the OCDM, as outlined in a previous section. OCDM reuses entities from SPAR ontologies to represent bibliographic entities (*fabio:Expression*), identifiers (*datacite:Identifier*), agent roles (*pro:RoleInTime*), responsible agents (*foaf:Agent*), and publication format details (*fabio:Manifestation*). The agent role serves as an intermediary between bibliographic resources and responsible agents, enabling the definition of time-dependent and context-dependent roles and statuses, such as author order [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

For example, in OpenCitations Meta, the entity with OMID *omid:br/062601067430* is titled Open Access and Online Publishing: A New Frontier In Nursing? (*dcterms:title*) and was published on 2012-07-25 (*prism:publicationDate*). According to the FRBR model, this article is considered the final published version, or an expression of the original work (*fabio:Expression*). It has an embodiment, represented by the entity *omid:re/06260837633* (*frbr:embodiment*), which corresponds to the printed version appearing on pages 1905-1908 of the journal volume (*prism:startingPage*, *prism:endingPage*). Specifically, the article is part of (*frbr:partOf*) issue number 9 (*fabio:hasSequenceIdentifier*) in volume 68 (*fabio:JournalVolume*)

of the Journal of Advanced Nursing (*fabio:Journal*) [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Additionally, Glenn Hunt (*foaf:Agent*), with given name (*foaf:givenName*) and family name (*foaf:familyName*), is the first author (*pro:RoleInTime*) of this article (*pro:isDocumentContextFor*). Likewise, Michelle Cleary is listed as the second author (*pro:hasNext*). This publication is also assigned an OpenCitations Meta Identifier, *omid:id/062601093630* (*datacite:hasIdentifier*), which is an entity of type *datacite:Identifier*. It is given an external identifier based on the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) scheme (*datacite:usesIdentifierScheme*), with the literal value “10.1111/j.13665-2648-2012.06023.x” (*literal:hasLiteralValue*). Once the mapping process is complete, the RDF data can be stored and uploaded to a triple-store [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Creator - provenance and change tracking

In addition to managing metadata, emphasis is placed on tracking provenance and changes for entities in OpenCitations Meta. Provenance captures details about who processed a particular entity - whether it was created, deleted, modified, or merged - when the action took place, and the primary source of the data. Tracking this information is crucial for maintaining the reliability and integrity of the metadata within OpenCitations Meta [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

In addition to storing provenance information, systems to track the evolution of entities are essential, particularly in activities like research assessments, where changes, whether from corrections or misclassifications, can affect the overall evaluation of scholars, research groups, or institutions. For instance, an institution’s name may change over time, and if these changes are not properly tracked, it can be difficult to identify all versions of the institution’s name and associated units without knowledge of its history. This challenge is mitigated by tracking how data evolves within the database, allowing users to understand these changes without requiring external background information. No other semantic database of scholarly metadata tracks changes and provenance in the standard RDF 1.1 format. OpenCitations’ provenance mechanism includes an initial creation snapshot for each entity, followed by subsequent snapshots that document modifications, merges, or deletions, each identified with a unique snapshot number [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

The challenge of provenance modeling and change-tracking in RDF has been extensively discussed in scholarly literature, yet no single standard has fully addressed both aspects. Consequently, OpenCitations employs well-established approaches, including named graphs, PROV-O, and Dublin Core. Specifically, each snapshot is linked to its predecessor through the *prov:wasDerivedFrom* predicate and is connected to the entity it describes via *prov:specializationOf*. Each snapshot also corresponds to a named graph that contains provenance metadata, such as the responsible agent (*prov:wasAttributedTo*), the primary source (*prov:hadPrimarySource*), the generation time (*prov:generatedAtTime*), and, when relevant, the invalidation time (*prov:invalidatedAtTime*) following the creation of a new snapshot. Optionally, each snapshot can include a natural language description of the changes that occurred (*dcterms:description*) [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

Additionally, OCDM introduces a new predicate, *oco:hasUpdateQuery*, defined

within the OpenCitations Ontology, which captures the delta between two versions of an entity using a SPARQL UPDATE query. The deduplication process, as described in previous sections, is applied not only to the current state of the data, but also to its entire history through a change-tracking mechanism. This ensures that if an identifier is traced back to an entity deleted from the triple-store, it will be associated with the OMID of the deleted entity. In cases where the deletion is part of a merge chain, the OMID of the resulting entity takes precedence [Massari, Heibi, Peroni et al., 2024].

2.2.5 OpenCitations Index

One of the first collections released by OpenCitations in 2018 was the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations (COCI). This collection featured DOI-to-DOI citation links extracted from the reference lists of articles indexed in Crossref’s database. The introduction of COCI was a key milestone for both the OpenCitations infrastructure and the Open Science community, as it provided a large, machine-readable set of open citation data, serving as an alternative to widely used subscription-based sources. All citations in COCI were defined according to the OCDM, as detailed earlier in this dissertation, utilizing Semantic Web technologies. Between December 2022 and November 2023, OpenCitations’ ingestion workflow was revamped, allowing for the expansion of open citation data within OpenCitations collections. This update brought in additional data from new sources, including NIH-OCC, DataCite, OpenAIRE, and JaLC. Today, all citation data is consolidated into a comprehensive collection known as the OpenCitations Index [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024].

Representing citation data

To handle large datasets of citation information from various, often overlapping sources, OpenCitations has developed specialized software components. These components enable metadata crosswalks between existing and potential new sources and the OCDM, as well as the deduplication of entities to avoid multiple representations of the same citation link. For instance, the same citation between bibliographic resources might appear across different sources, each using different identifiers for the same resources. The process for ingesting new data into the OpenCitations Index was designed in accordance with the OCDM’s citation modeling framework. OCDM incorporates several concepts from the Citation Typing Ontology, with the *cito:Citation* class used to define a permanent, conceptual directional link from the citing bibliographic entity to the cited bibliographic entity [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024].

The *cito:Citation* class offers a machine-readable specification for each citation, treating it as a first-class data entity with its own associated metadata, which includes [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024]:

- The citing entity, represented by the property *cito:hasCitingEntity*, referring to the bibliographic resource acting as the source of the citation.

- The cited entity, represented by the property *cito:hasCitedEntity*, referring to the bibliographic resource being cited.
- The citation creation date, represented by the property *cito:hasCitationCreationDate*, which marks the date the citation was created, usually corresponding to the publication date of the citing entity.
- The citation timespan, represented by the property *cito:hasCitationTimespan*, indicating the interval between the publication dates of the citing and cited entities, expressed using the XML Schema datatype for time duration.
- The type of citation, represented by two subclasses of *cito:Citation* (*cito:AuthorSelfCitation* and *cito:JournalSelfCitation*), which describe citations where the citing and cited entities share at least one author in common, or are published in the same journal, respectively.

OpenCitations Index methodology

The process of ingesting citation data from the original source into the OpenCitations Index starts with the CSV file set generated during the "Source preprocess" step, as outlined in the "Current workflow" section. Each citation is represented by two entities in these files, structured in a two-column tabular format. The citations in these tables represent links between two potentially persistent identifiers, depending on the source from which the data was collected. To prepare the citation data for ingestion into the OpenCitations Index, the citation links must be converted into an OMID-to-OMID format. This conversion relies on the content of the Redis database created during the "Meta process," which contains the mapping between the original persistent identifiers used in the source and the OMIDs generated in the previous step. For instance, if a citation link from a source uses DOIs as persistent identifiers for both the citing and cited entities, we first query Redis to retrieve the corresponding OMIDs for each DOI. The DOI-to-DOI citation link is then converted into an OMID-to-OMID citation link [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024].

At the conclusion of this step, two main outputs are generated. Full dumps of citation data, formatted according to the data model derived from the source information, are provided in RDF, CSV, and JSON Scholix formats. These dumps contain new citations added to the OpenCitations Index, along with their corresponding metadata. The OpenCitations Index graph database (a triple-store) is updated with OMID-to-OMID citation links in RDF format, without additional metadata. In this structure, each citation is uniquely identified by a persistent Open Citation Identifier, as previously described [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024].

Provenance, change tracking and dataset metadata

In addition to storing citation data in the OpenCitations Index, the process also tracks the provenance and versioning of each citation. Consistent with the OCDM specification, which reuses terms from PROV-O, each citation is defined by one or more provenance snapshots—instances of *prov:Entity* that capture the entity's

status (linked through the *prov:specializationOf* property) at a given point in time. Each snapshot includes records of validity and invalidity dates, responsible agents for the creation or modification of the metadata, primary data sources, and a SPARQL query that summarizes changes relative to previous snapshots, implemented via the *oco:hasUpdateQuery* property defined in OCDM. The *prov:atLocation* property tracks the internal collection (one for each data source) where citations are organized. Additionally, the metadata description for the entire dataset defined by the OpenCitations Index is included, documenting when it was modified and specifying the dump distributions published alongside the collection. To describe this data, two additional ontologies—VoID and DCAT—are employed. Specifically, a *dcat:Dataset* containing citation information is detailed with cataloging information and distribution data (*dcat:Distribution*), which includes specifications for licenses, dumps, media types, and data volumes [Heibi, Moretti, Peroni, Soricetti, 2024].

2.3 Framework review

For the implementation of the practical part of the dissertation, a framework for the development of automated pipelines has to be selected first. In this section, four main candidates will be introduced and shortly examined - Apache Airflow, Prefect, Celery and Luigi.

2.3.1 Apache Airflow

Apache Airflow is an open-source workflow management platform for data engineering pipelines, released under the Apache 2.0 licence. The work on the project started at Airbnb in 2014 and was first released in June 2015. Apache Airflow utilises standard Python feature to create workflows, and comes with a modern web application for workflow monitoring, scheduling and managing. “Airflow works best with workflows that are mostly static and slowly changing. [...] For high-volume, data-intensive tasks, a best practice is to delegate to external services specializing in that type of work”, which coincides with the scope of the practical part of the dissertation. In addition to being available via pip, there are community-created Docker images with the latest stable Debian OS, Python installation, libraries required to connect to supported databases and a predefined set of providers. Airflow is able to run on POSIX-compliant OSes, and is tested in development on popular Linux distributions and recent macOS versions; it can be run on Windows via Windows Subsystem for Linux 2 or Linux Containers, but native support is currently not available and is not perceived as being of high priority. [Airflow, 2025a] Example of a simple code snippet defining a DAG (authored workflow orchestrating tasks) echoing “hello” in bash [Airflow, 2025b]:

```
1 from datetime import datetime
2 from airflow.sdk import DAG, task
3 from airflow.providers.standard.operators.bash import BashOperator
4 # A DAG represents a workflow, a collection of tasks
5 with DAG(dag_id="demo", start_date=datetime(2022, 1, 1), schedule="
   0 0 * * *") as dag:
6     # Tasks are represented as operators
7     hello = BashOperator(task_id="hello", bash_command="echo hello"
8     )
9     @task()
10    def airflow():
11        print("airflow")
12    # Set dependencies between tasks
13    hello >> airflow()
```

2.3.2 Prefect

Prefect OSS is a workflow orchestration framework for building data pipelines in Python, released under the Apache 2.0 licence. Prefect 3.0 was released in 2024 [Prefect, 2025a]. Just like Apache Airflow, utilises standard Python feature to create workflows, and has it’s own web application for workflow monitoring. Prefect is not bound to POSIX-compliant OSes like Apache Airflow is due to it’s choice of libraries,

so it can be ran on Windows out of the box and deployed anywhere as long as Python can be ran. The other core features of Prefect are: robust state management, being event-driven (e.g. flows can be triggered on schedules or external events and paused for human intervention) and creating tasks dynamically at runtime [Prefect, 2025b]. Prefect also offers a commercial version of the framework centred on cloud connectivity and aimed at enterprise-level workflow management.

Example of a code snippet running a simple workflow every day at 08:00 [Prefect, 2025c]:

```
1 from prefect import flow, task
2 import random
3 @task
4 def get_customer_ids() -> list[str]:
5     # Fetch customer IDs from a database or API
6     return [f"customer{n}" for n in random.choices(range(100), k
7     =10)]
8 @task
9 def process_customer(customer_id: str) -> str:
10    # Process a single customer
11    return f"Processed {customer_id}"
12 @flow
13 def main() -> list[str]:
14    customer_ids = get_customer_ids()
15    # Map the process_customer task across all customer IDs
16    results = process_customer.map(customer_ids)
17    return results
18 if __name__ == "__main__":
19    main.serve(
20        name="my-first-deployment",
21        cron="0 8 * * *" # Run every day at 8:00 AM
22    )
```

2.3.3 Celery

Celery is an open source asynchronous tasks queue based on distributed message passing between clients and workers written in Python. It requires a message broker (most commonly Redis) to run. Celery is released under BSD-3-Clause licence. To initiate a task, a client puts a message on the queue, which is then delivered by the broker to a worker (in this specific case, a worker would be one of the tools used in the OpenCitations workflow). The protocol can be technically implemented in any language, either by way of clients or by using webhooks [Celery, 2025a]. Celery does not need configuration files, and utilises standard Python features like decorators to create workflows. The developers of Celery do not support Windows. [Celery, 2025b]

An example workflow [Celery, 2025c] with the project layout:

```
1 src/
2   proj/__init__.py
3     /celery.py
4     /tasks.py
```

```
1 proj/celery.py:
2 from celery import Celery
```

```

3 app = Celery('proj',
4             broker='amqp://',
5             backend='rpc://',
6             include=['proj.tasks'])
7 # Optional configuration, see the application user guide.
8 app.conf.update(
9     result_expires=3600,
10 )
11 if __name__ == '__main__':
12     app.start()

```

```

1 proj/tasks.py:
2 from .celery import app
3 @app.task
4 def add(x, y):
5     return x + y
6 @app.task
7 def mul(x, y):
8     return x * y
9 @app.task
10 def xsum(numbers):
11     return sum(numbers)

```

is started with a terminal command:

```

1 $ celery -A proj worker -l INFO

```

2.3.4 Luigi

Luigi is a Python package for building pipelines of batch jobs, which handles dependency resolution, workflow management, visualisation, handling failures, etc. It was started internally at Spotify and open-sourced in late 2012 under Apache 2.0 licence. Luigi's self-stated process is “to address all the plumbing typically associated with long-running batch process. You want to chain many tasks, automate them, and failures will happen”, which coincides with the practical part of the dissertation. Luigi comes with a web interface visualiser and dependency graphs. Luigi does not use external configuration files. Being just a Python package, it can be ran on any environment supporting Python. [Spotify, 2025]

An example snippet defining a Luigi task extracting a list of links to the most-read books on Project Gutenberg [Gilligan, 2021]:

```

1 import requests
2 import luigi
3 from bs4 import BeautifulSoup
4 class GetTopBooks(luigi.Task):
5     def output(self):
6         return luigi.LocalTarget("data/books_list.txt")
7     def run(self):
8         resp = requests.get("http://www.gutenberg.org/browse/scores/top")
9         soup = BeautifulSoup(resp.content, "html.parser")
10        pageHeader = soup.find_all("h2", string="Top 100 EBooks yesterday")[0]
11        listTop = pageHeader.find_next_sibling("ol")
12        with self.output().open("w") as f:

```

```
13         for result in listTop.select("li>a"):
14             if "/ebooks/" in result["href"]:
15                 f.write("http://www.gutenberg.org{link}.txt.utf
-8\n"
16                     .format(
17                         link=result["href"]
18                     )
19                 )
```

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Requirements analysis

This section will outline the use case scenario and associated use case descriptions, as well as the user requirements assigned with MoSCoW priority, that is, which requirements **M**ust be included, **S**hould be included, **C**an be included, or **W**on't be included in the final version of the application.

3.1.1 Use case scenario and use case descriptions

Figure 3.1: Use case scenario

ID	1
----	---

Goal:	User runs the automatised workflow, and receives a notification upon its' end.
Primary actor:	User - Person tasked with generating an update for OpenCitations' databases.
Preconditions:	The necessary input files have been generated. The necessary OpenCitations tools are located on the same computer.
Postconditions:	The databases used by OpenCitations tools are updated. The output files have been generated. The user is notified after the automatised workflow concludes.
Main flow:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User specifies the localisation of the input and output files. 2. User configures preprocessing, validation, database update and file generation options. 3. User runs the automatised workflow. 4. The values from the configuration file are validated. 5. <i>preprocess</i> tool preprocesses the input files, checking for data alignment for subsequent tools. 6. <i>validation</i> tool validates the input CSV files. 7. <i>oc_meta</i> tool updates the <i>META</i> and <i>PROV</i> databases with new information on bibliographic metadata. 8. <i>oc_meta_val</i> tool validates the updates, reading from the <i>META</i> and <i>PROV</i> databases. 9. <i>oc_meta_csv</i> tool produces a new CSV file with updates reading from the <i>META</i> database. 10. <i>meta2redis</i> tool creates a REDIS database in RAM with the new information 11. <i>cnc</i> tool updates the <i>PROV</i> database with citation information from the validated CSV file and the REDIS in-RAM database. 12. <i>cits2redis</i> tool updates the INDEX database with new citation information. 13. <i>dump_index</i> tool produces raw data on new citation information. 14. user receives a notification about the conclusion of the workflow.
Alternate flow:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4a. Validation of the configuration options fails if one of the values will not be accepted by the tools. 4b. Go to main flow step 14. 6a. <i>validation</i> tool fails if the user configured the tool to fail the entire validation upon unsuccessful validation of an entry. 6b. Go to main flow step 14.

3.1.2 Graphical representation of the workflow

Figure 3.2: Existing OpenCitations workflow

Figure 3.2 depicts the existing OpenCitations workflow, which is examined in detail in the *Literature review* chapter. The planned work for the workflow automation is delimited with the double red rectangle. Within it, the OpenCitations’ tools being used are depicted with blue rounded rectangles, with purple rectangles showing which step of the use case scenario they correspond to. The red and yellow cylinders represent permanent and temporary databases. The green figures represent files (in CSV, TTL and other formats). Arrows pointing towards a tool represent reading data, while arrows pointing from a tool represent writing data to files or databases.

Figure 3.3: Planned automated workflow

Figure 3.3 depicts the planned steps of the automated workflow, which will be further described in the *Implementation* chapter. The steps are represented with the purple rounded rectangles, and the corresponding OpenCitations' tools have been put next to them in blue rounded rectangles. As in the previous figure, the permanent databases have been depicted as red cylinders, the temporary database as yellow cylinder, and files (in CSV, TTL and other formats) as remaining green figures. Dotted arrows represent reading from or writing to files and databases, while full arrows represents the sequence in the execution of steps. Files that are not published as part of the datasets have been omitted from this diagram.

3.1.3 User requirements

ID	Description	Priority
UR-1	The application must implement the workflow automatization with all tools running in correct order in a single file.	M
UR-2	The application must allow the user to specify the location of the input CSV documents.	M
UR-3	The application must allow the user to specify the location of any output documents.	M
UR-4	The application must have configurable options regarding validation, whether to stop the entire workflow upon failing to validate an entry, or to remove the entry and continue.	M
UR-5	The application must have appropriate error handling and logging; if a tool fails, a report stating what and why has failed, with a log for debugging purposes.	M
UR-6	The application must correctly pass through and save all tool-specific flags.	M
UR-7	The application should be implemented in Python, as is the rest of OpenCitations tools.	S
UR-8	The application should prompt the user or require an explicit overwrite flag if output files already exist in the specified directory.	S
UR-9	The application should write logs to a text file.	S
UR-10	The application should notify the user upon the completion of the workflow.	S
UR-11	The application could show a summary report at the end of the execution (if it is possible according to the existing tool implementation)	C
UR-12	The application could allow for simulating execution without producing any output.	C
UR-13	The application could support CLI arguments and configuration files.	C
UR-14	The application will not have a graphical interface.	W
UR-15	The application will not modify tool logic, they are treated as working as is.	W
UR-16	The application will not implement parallel execution of steps (which is also seemingly impossible with relation to the current workflow) to facilitate reading logs.	W

3.2 Evaluation strategy

The application will be evaluated in the following manner. First, the analysis of the fulfilment of user requirements will be carried out. After that, a two-step evaluation of the automatization will follow:

1. First, the automatization will be run on a personal computer with all the tools necessary to complete the automated part of the workflow installed and configured. The CSV files used as input will be taken from existing Meta and Index dumps and trimmed as to be accepted by the *preprocess* tool. As all the tools described in the workflow are already implemented, there are no plans to modify them. Therefore, this first part will be evaluated on the successful completion of the workflow, basing on the generation of output files and modification of the databases.
2. After the successful evaluation of the first step, the workflow will be tested for the failure points, i.e. the alternative flows as described in the use case scenario. This will be done by preparing a configuration file with erroneous values, as well as input files that contain errors to provoke errors in *preprocess* and *validation* tools. Upon the successful completion of the entire flow in the use case scenario, the practical part of the dissertation will be considered complete.

The evaluation chapter will also include the evaluation of the risk planning strategies introduced in the next section.

3.3 Project management

This section provides an outline for the management of the project; an in-depth risk analysis and potential PLES (Professional, Legal, Ethical and Social) issues related to the technical part of the dissertation.

3.3.1 Risk analysis

Risk types, probability, effect and priority

First, the different types of risks that may occur during the development of the project have to be identified. Additionally, the chance of the risks happening (probability), the potential impact of those risks on occurrence (effect) and the combination of both (priority) need to be identified in order to conduct appropriate planning and monitoring.

Risks can be mainly attributed to the following two types:

- Technology – related to the tools used for the project, as well as the other technological aspects of software development (IDEs, libraries, etc.)
- Estimation – related to estimation of time and effort required to fulfil the aims and objectives, as well as the aims and objectives themselves.

The probability of the occurrence of a risk can be categorised as follows:

Very low, low, moderate, high, very high.

The effect of a risk, may it happen, can be categorised as follows:

- Negligible – The overall effect of the event is minimal, or there is no effect.
- Insignificant – The overall effect of the event will result in a loss of a small number of working hours.
- Bearable – The overall effect of the event will result in a loss of a day of work, put minor obstacles on the road to finish the project successfully, or similar.
- Serious – The overall effect of the event will result in a loss of up to a week of work, put major obstacles on the road to finish the project successfully, or similar.
- Calamitous – The overall effect of the event will result in a loss of more than a week of work, making the project impossible to finish successfully, or similar.

The priority a risk needs to be addressed to can be categorised as low, medium or high.

Identification of risks and risk analysis

After identifying the criteria for rating, the risks themselves can now be identified and analysed:

ID	Type	Risk	Description
R-T1	Technology	Loss of code or documentation	The documents and/or the code of the project may be lost due to workstation malfunction, being misplaced, destroyed accidentally or lost because of malicious software.
R-T2	Technology	Limitations of technology	The technology chosen to be used may not be able to support the fulfilment of the requirements specified for the project.
R-T3	Technology	Unfamiliarity of technology	The technology chosen to be used may be unfamiliar to the person developing the project.
R-E1	Estimation	Underestimation of resources and time required	The resources and time needed to complete the project may be underestimated during the planning phase.

ID	Risk	Probability	Effect	Priority
R-T1	Loss of code or documentation	Very low	Calamitous	Medium
R-T2	Limitations of technology	Low	Serious	Medium
R-T3	Unfamiliarity of technology	Moderate	Serious	High
R-E1	Underestimation of resources and time required	Moderate	Serious	High

Risk planning

After identifying and analysing the risk, strategies aiming to manage them may be developed as well. These are categorised in a following way:

- Avoidance – reduction of probability that a risk is going to happen
- Minimisation – reduction of impact of the risks once it happens
- Contingency – actions undertaken after the risk happens

ID	Category	Strategy
R-T1	Avoidance	Use of a version control system with remote repository (e.g. Git with GitHub)
R-T1	Avoidance	Frequent commits with describing commit messages
R-T1	Avoidance	Storing copies of the thesis document and code in cloud storage
R-T1	Minimisation	Periodic manual backups
R-T1	Minimisation	Partial separation of raw data, generated output and source code
R-T1	Minimisation	Clear directory structure to avoid accidental deletion
R-T1	Contingency	Restoration of the repository to a previous commit
R-T1	Contingency	Recloning the remote repository onto a new machine
R-T1	Contingency	Regeneration of the intermediate files using the reproducible workflow
ID	Category	Strategy
R-T2	Avoidance	Analysing possible workflow managers before implementation
R-T2	Avoidance	Choosing technologies with active documentation and support
R-T2	Avoidance	Selecting Docker-based deployment where applicable to isolate environments
R-T2	Contingency	Replacing individual components
R-T2	Contingency	Limiting scope to supported features while documenting constraints

ID	Category	Strategy
R-T3	Avoidance	Preliminary experimentation with new technologies before integrating them into the workflow
R-T3	Avoidance	Reading documentation and studying example configurations
R-T3	Avoidance	Starting with a proof-of-concept pipeline before expanding it further to include tools
R-T3	Minimisation	Developing the workflow incrementally
R-T3	Minimisation	Use of logging and explicit error handling
R-T3	Minimisation	Debugging via container inspection
R-T3	Contingency	Consulting documentation and issue trackers
R-T3	Contingency	Pinning versions of dependencies to avoid unexpected behavioural changes

ID	Category	Strategy
R-E1	Avoidance	Breaking down the project into clearly defined phases
R-E1	Avoidance	Identifying dependencies early
R-E1	Avoidance	Including buffer time in planning
R-E1	Minimisation	Developing the workflow incrementally
R-E1	Minimisation	Preparing a small example input dataset for testing purposes
R-E1	Minimisation	Reusing existing OpenCitations' utilities where possible
R-E1	Contingency	Reducing input dataset size for evaluation
R-E1	Contingency	Narrowing evaluation scope to workflow-level validation
R-E1	Contingency	Prioritising core functionality over optional features
R-E1	Contingency	Freezing feature development to grant time for documentation

Risk monitoring

The last step of the risk analysis is risk monitoring, where the previously identified and analysed risks are assessed and evaluated.

ID	Risk	Indicators
R-T1	Loss of code or documentation	Code/documents missing
R-T2	Limitations of technology	Unknown specifically, but related to R-P2 and R-T3.
R-T3	Unfamiliarity of technology	Inability to perform personally set tasks.
R-E1	Underestimation of resources and time required	Struggling to keep up with personally set deadlines.

3.3.2 Professional, Legal, Ethical and Social Issues

Consideration of Professional Issues

The project will be delivered in a professional manner, i.e. the planning for it needs to be realistic, with a set amount of time used solely for the reason of code development and documenting the development each week. Additionally, weekly meetings with the project supervisor will be held to inform and receive feedback on the work done during the previous week, as a part of the weekly OpenCitations group meetings scheduled on Tuesday mornings. Backups of all code and documentation will be done at the end of every workday, both on external physical data storage units and on cloud storage.

Consideration of Legal Issues

The project itself is focused on the automatization of the process of creating the OpenCitations database. The automatization itself does not deal with any personal data, hence it is believed that it is going to automatically going to be developed with full accordance to GDPR. In regards to the development process, the primary objective of the project is to deliver an automatization method that will conform to the OpenCitations' CC0 distribution license. Other automatization methods will be explored, but will be considered as "additional", i.e. serving more of an exercise role to get experience with (if possible) existing state-of-the-art automatization tools.

Consideration of Ethical Issues

The project itself is focused on implementing an automatised process of creating the OpenCitations database. The automatization itself does not seem to raise any ethical issues, therefore they are not believed to be raised in the scope of this dissertation.

Consideration of Social Issues

The project itself is focused on implementing an automatised process of creating the OpenCitations database. The automatization itself does not seem to raise any social issues, therefore they are not believed to be raised in the scope of this dissertation.

3.4 Framework selection

Between the four previously introduced frameworks, I have decided to write the practical part of the dissertation using Luigi.

The principal factor of not selecting Apache Airflow was its inability to run on Windows out of the box. Of course, this is due to raise eyebrows, considering the entire point of the project is to develop an automated workflow for creating an open database; but I would like to argue that I want my project to simply run on the most common operating systems, the list of which Windows is definitely a part of. Additionally, while having a mandatory web-server for monitoring the workflow and a mandatory scheduler, Airflow also requires an additional metadata database, adding to additional overflow that I would like to avoid as much as necessary.

Aside from suffering the same problem with Windows as Apache Airflow, Celery answers a different problem domain, namely, it is a distributed task queue; its asynchronous nature is useless with the way the workflow is organised at the moment. Furthermore, Celery does require a message broker, usually Redis, which by itself is not a problem, but it is used throughout the workflow for storing data, and I would rather avoid potential conflicts; and a result back-end, which circles back to the point about additional overflow. Finally, tasks in Celery are designed to return values, which is not good for expressing the necessary persistent results.

Prefect's main issue is its origin in a closed-source product oriented towards being cloud-native via proprietary cloud solutions and APIs. Next, there is the lack of maturity, as Prefect is extremely new, being released in 2024, and as it is developing and evolving, some changes may be introduced, that would break the existing implementation of the workflow. Lastly, while file-based semantics do exist, Prefect's definitions focus more on parametrised function flows.

Starting with the positive factors; Luigi, being a pure-Python library, is more lightweight, especially in comparison to Apache Airflow and Celery, and does not need any additional overhead in the form of web-servers, databases, etc. It has the built-in flexibility to use a central scheduler, which also enables the use of a web application for workflow monitoring; achieving this is just a matter of running a *luigid* command in the terminal. Additionally, Luigi's structure is easily readable, that is, the workflow is based on *Tasks*, which methods *require()*, *output()*, and *run()* define other *Tasks*, that have to be completed beforehand, the expected output created after finishing the *Task*, and the actual code being run. Finally, Luigi seems to be in the "sweet spot" when it comes to maturity, being stable and widely used, but without forcing "trendy" solutions like cloud abstractions.

There is one aspect of Luigi that has to be discussed here, which I have trouble with describing as neutral at best. Each *Task* has a method *output()*, which specifies *luigi.Targets*, in this case *luigi.LocalTargets* as we are interested in storing files locally. If the workflow had to be designed from the ground up, this would not be problematic, as the way of designing the output of each step would lie in my hands. The main problem here lies in the uncertainty of the number and names of the files, which would have to be known beforehand in order to be specified in the *output()*, since the existence of the file is the main check for whether or not a *Task* has been finished. Furthermore, the tools that serve as the principal blocks of each step have already been designed and written in the past years, as evidenced by Section 2 of

the dissertation. This means that although Luigi's tasks are file-oriented, I did have to resort to using dummy TXT files instead of specifying the actual output of the called scripts as a way to confirm that each task has run successfully. Same can be said for the scripts that do not result in any files being created, such as *meta2redis*.

Aside from *output()*, classes extending *luigi.Task*, i.e. defining tasks, have two other compulsory functions; *requires()* contains an object or a list of objects representing other classes extending *luigi.Task*, that need to be completed before the current task can start executing; and *run()*, which contains the actual logic behind the task.

Chapter 4

Implementation

In this chapter, the implementation of the automated workflow will be explained; this will be followed by the explanation to minor bugfixes made for the OpenCitations' tools during the development cycle, as well as minor scripts that were used to help with the development and testing of the main workflow. Example code of the block acting as the main function, as well as the first Luigi task has been added to provide some insight into the inner workings of the workflow.

4.1 Automated workflow

Figure 4.1 depicts the planned steps of the automated workflow, which will be further described in the *Implementation* chapter. The steps are represented with the purple rounded rectangles, and the corresponding OpenCitations' tools have been put next to them in blue rounded rectangles. Orange rounded rectangles represent *virtuoso_utilities*, a OpenCitations' helper package for management of OpenLink Virtuoso, which is not part of neither META, nor INDEX scripts. The permanent databases have been depicted as red cylinders, the temporary databases hosted as Docker instances as yellow cylinder, and files (in CSV, TTL and other formats) as remaining green figures. Dotted arrows represent reading from or writing to files and databases, while full arrows represents the sequence in the execution of steps. Files that are not published as part of the datasets have been omitted from this diagram.

Figure 4.1: Implemented automated workflow

4.1.1 Main function

```

1 if __name__ == "__main__":
2     freeze_support();
3
4     parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(add_help=True);
5     parser.add_argument(
6         "--local-scheduler",
7         action="store_true",
8         help="Use Luigi's local in-process scheduler instead of a
9         central luigid.",
10    );
11    args, _unknown = parser.parse_known_args();
12
13    load_config();
14
15    tasks_to_run = [

```

```

15     Preprocess(),
16     Validation(),
17     DatabaseSwitchOn(),
18     OCMeta(),
19     OCMetaCsv(),
20     Meta2Redis(),
21     OCIndexCNC(),
22     OCIndexCits2Redis(),
23     OCIndexDump(),
24     VirtuosoDump(),
25     Cleanup()
26 ];
27
28 try:
29     ok = luigi.build(
30         tasks_to_run,
31         workers=1,
32         local_scheduler=bool(args.local_scheduler),
33         scheduler_host="127.0.0.1",
34         scheduler_port=8082,
35         detailed_summary=True
36     );
37
38     if ok:
39         notify("Workflow Status", "Workflow finished.", True);
40         raise SystemExit(0);
41     else:
42         notify("Workflow Status", "Workflow finished.", False);
43         raise SystemExit(1);
44
45 except Exception as e:
46     notify("Workflow Status", f"Workflow finished:\n{str(e)}",
47         False);
48     raise;

```

The `__main__` block is responsible for the execution of the entire workflow. It begins with a call to `freeze_support()`, which is a standard compatibility requirement for Python's multiprocessing on Windows systems; unlike POSIX-compliant systems, Windows cannot fork processes and must spawn new Python interpreters instead, thus the use of this function ensures that any subprocesses created by Luigi are initialised safely, without re-executing the entire script recursively. However, this is left as a safeguard for any potential extensions of the workflow, since the current workflow has no parallel execution of tasks by design.

Next, the script defines an argument parser that exposes a single optional flag, `--local-scheduler`. This is left mainly for debugging purposes, and if run without this flag, the script necessitates running *luigid* central scheduler service first, which also gives access to Luigi's web application front end. The call to `parse_known_args()` is intentional, as Luigi injects its own arguments when tasks are launched via its CLI, so this approach allows the script to accept my own custom arguments, while ignoring any unrecognised ones instead of failing.

`Tasks.to_run` defines the root tasks of the workflow. For the sake of readability, it is presented in the sequence it is designed to run in. The correct execution order is determined by Luigi, which also ensures that each task is only executed once and only if the specified outputs are missing.

Luigi.build() call triggers the execution of the pipeline, taking several configuration parameters: the number of workers, selecting between local and central scheduler, parameters for host and port of the central scheduler, and the additional diagnostic output upon completion.

Finally, the script exits with a conventional Unix-style exit code and a call to the helper function *notify*, which creates an OS notification pop-up informing that the workflow has terminated. A successful pipeline run results in exit code 0, while any error leading to a failure of a task produces exit code 1. Raising *SystemExit* explicitly ensures that external tools, be it other scripts, continuous integration systems, workflow supervisors, can reliably detect success or failure and react accordingly.

4.1.2 Helper functions

wait_for_port

The first of the helper functions, *wait_for_port()* is used to block execution until a network service becomes available. It repeatedly attempts to open a TCP connection to a specified host on a specified port, retrying every 500 milliseconds until either a connection is successfully established, or a configurable timeout is reached.

This behaviour is important for interacting with Docker-based services used during the workflow, such as Apache Jena Fuseki or Redis. Although a container is appearing to be running, the service inside it requires additional time to initialise and bind to its network port. Without the *wait*, sending SPARQL queries or issuing Redis commands could fail due to timing issues. If no successful connection is made before the timeout elapses, the function raises a *TimeoutError*. The error message includes the last exception observed, useful for debugging.

docker_rm

Docker_rm() contains the logic required to forcefully remove a Docker container after providing its name. It delegates execution to the aforementioned *run()* function with arguments *rm -f < container >*; the *-f* (force) flag ensures that the container is terminated and removed even if it is not currently stopped, which simplifies cleanup logic and avoids the need for separate stop and remove operations.

Standard output and error streams are suppressed to prevent cluttering the workflow logs with routine Docker messages, so only meaningful information such as explicit errors appear in the terminal; container removal is an expected operation within the pipeline.

The call is wrapped in a try-except block and ignores *CalledProcessError* exceptions, as attempting to remove a container that either does not exist, or is already stopped should not result in an interruption of the workflow. *Docker_rm()* is used ubiquitously throughout the workflow as a standard mechanism to clear and reset the state of Docker services.

get_nested_yaml

Get_nested_yaml() function provides a convenient mechanism for retrieving values from a hierarchically structured YAML configuration dictionary using a dotted key path. YAML configuration files represent data in nested mappings (e.g. `index.identifier.pmid`), but accessing such nested fields directly through chained dictionary lookups can be error-prone and verbose.

The function addresses this by iterating through the dictionary; the dotted key is split into its individual components, and each component is used to traverse one level deeper into the nested structure. If an expected key is missing, or the structure does not match the expected dictionary format, the function returns a user-provided default value. This avoids *KeyError* exceptions and allows for handling partially defined configuration files.

In the context of the workflow, *get_nested_yaml()* is used when constructing the *config.ini* file required by OC Index scripts. This file aggregates several configuration values drawn from the main YAML configuration file. Using dotted paths simplifies the mapping between the YAML and INI formats, as well as improves potential maintainability.

expect_in

Expect_in function serves as a configurable validation and normalisation layer for values loaded from the YAML configuration file. At its core, the function retrieves the configuration entry *name* from the dictionary *cfg*. If the entry is missing, it records an error or inserts a default value back into the configuration. This adds the possibility of defining optional parameters with sensible fallback behaviour while detecting genuinely missing mandatory fields.

Among supported forms of validation are: type casting (*type*) for some scripts that require a specific type for some of its variables, transformation (*transformation*) for more complex preprocessing (although in practice, it's only used to transform a string to lowercase), and membership validation (*allowed*) for parameters that serve as binary flags. Every successfully validated value is written back into the same configuration dictionary.

Within the workflow, this function is used during the *load_config* helper function to validate and standardise configuration entries before they are consumed by downstream tasks.

notify

The *notify()* helper function provides a lightweight, cross-platform mechanism for signalling the completion status of the workflow to the user through system-level notifications. Its purpose is purely communicative: to inform the user whether the execution has finished successfully or terminated with an error, without requiring manual inspection of the terminal output.

At its core, the function determines the operating system at runtime using the *platform.system()* call. Based on the detected environment, it selects an appropriate native notification mechanism. If the platform is not recognised, the function gracefully degrades to printing the message to the standard output.

The optional *success* parameter controls the semantic tone of the notification. Rather than altering the structure of the message, it influences the visual representation (for example, informational versus error icon), thereby providing immediate contextual feedback. This design keeps the interface minimal while still conveying essential execution state information.

Within the workflow, this function is called at the end of the *main* execution block to report the overall outcome. By abstracting the notification logic into a dedicated helper, the implementation remains platform-independent at the orchestration level, while still offering user-friendly feedback across Windows, macOS and Linux environments.

clean_directory_except

Clean_directory_except() provides controlled, selective deletion of files and subdirectories within a given subdirectory. Its purpose is to remove all temporary or intermediate artefacts produced during the workflow while preserving only a small number of explicitly specified files or folders.

The function takes two arguments, *base_dir*, the directory to be cleaned, and *keep*, a list of names that should remain untouched. It iterates over every entry in the directory, and skips an entry if its name appears in the *keep* list. Otherwise, the function deletes it with *shutil.rmtree()* (if a directory), or *Path.unlink()* (in case of an individual file), suppressing errors in case a file is concurrently removed by another process or does not exist at the time of the deletion.

Clean_directory_except() is used in the final *CleanUp* task, where the workflow removes internal processing outputs that are not intended for publication or downstream reuse.

load_config

Load_config() is responsible for loading, validating, and normalising all configuration parameters supplied by the user in the *config.yaml* file. This begins by reading and parsing the YAML file into a Python dictionary.

YAML files may contain optional entries and/or user-provided values in various formats, and as such, the workflow must ensure that each parameter satisfies expected type and value constraints before any downstream task uses it. To achieve this, the helper function *expect_in()* is applied to each configuration key that needs to be specifically checked for its presence, correct typing, allowable values and transformations. This is done for ensuring that user errors occurring during the editing of the configuration file are detected early, reported in a clear and aggregated error message, and not wasting compute time on performing tasks if the workflow is not going to terminate successfully.

After all validated entries have been processed, each configuration value is assigned into the global namespace. This allows tasks to access the validated configuration parameters.

4.1.3 Task 1 - Preprocess

```

1 class Preprocess(luigi.Task):
2     param1 = luigi.PathParameter(default = "dir/temp/index-
3     preprocessed/success.txt");
4     param2 = luigi.PathParameter(default = "dir/temp/meta-
5     preprocessed/success.txt");
6
7     def requires(self):
8         return LoadConfig();
9
10    def output(self):
11        return [
12            luigi.LocalTarget(self.param1),
13            luigi.LocalTarget(self.param2)
14        ]
15
16    def run(self):
17        # preprocess in sparql
18        if(preprocess_storage_type == "sparql"):
19            try:
20                # parsing the sparql endpoint
21                u = urlparse(preprocess_sparql_endpoint);
22                host = u.hostname or "localhost";
23                port = u.port or (443 if u.scheme == "https" else
24                80);
25
26                parts = [p for p in (u.path or "").split("/") if p
27                ];
28
29                if not parts:
30                    raise ValueError(f"Cannot determine dataset
31                    from endpoint path: {preprocess_sparql_endpoint}");
32
33                if parts[-1].lower() in ("sparql", "query"):
34                    if len(parts) < 2:
35                        raise ValueError(f"Endpoint path too short
36                        to infer dataset: {preprocess_sparql_endpoint}");
37                    dataset = parts[-2];
38                else:
39                    dataset = parts[-1];
40
41                if host not in ("localhost", "127.0.0.1"):
42                    print(f"Endpoint host is '{host}'. This script
43                    exposes Fuseki on the local machine; \n please access it via
44                    http://localhost:{port}/{dataset}/sparql");
45
46                # running fuseki container in docker
47                docker_rm(fuseki_container);
48                run(["docker", "run", "-d", "--name",
49                fuseki_container, "-p", f"{port}:3030", fuseki_image, "--mem", f
50                "/{dataset}"]);
51                wait_for_port("localhost", port);
52                print(f"Fuseki ready at http://localhost:{port}/{
53                dataset}/sparql (requested: {preprocess_sparql_endpoint}");
54
55                # running preprocess for meta and index
56                cmd = ["python", preprocess_dir, input_dir + "/meta
57                ", temp_dir + "/meta-preprocessed", "--storage-type", "sparql",
58                "--sparql-endpoint", preprocess_sparql_endpoint];

```

```

45         run(cmd);
46         print("Input for meta preprocessed");
47         cmd = ["python", preprocess_dir, input_dir + "/"
index", temp_dir + "/index-preprocessed", "--storage-type", "
sparql", "--sparql-endpoint", preprocess_sparql_endpoint];
48         run(cmd);
49         print("Input for index preprocessed.");
50         finally:
51             docker_rm(fuseki_container);
52     # preprocess in redis
53     elif(preprocess_storage_type == "redis"):
54         try:
55             # running redis in docker
56             docker_rm(redis_container);
57             run(["docker", "run", "-d", "--name",
redis_container, "-p", f"{preprocess_redis_port}:6379",
redis_image]);
58             wait_for_port("localhost", preprocess_redis_port);
59             print(f"Redis ready at redis://localhost:{
preprocess_redis_port}");
60
61             #running preprocess for meta and index
62             cmd = ["python", preprocess_dir, input_dir + "/meta
", temp_dir + "/meta-preprocessed", "--storage-type", "redis", "
--redis-db", preprocess_redis_db_number];
63             run(cmd);
64             print("Input for meta preprocessed");
65             cmd = ["python", preprocess_dir, input_dir + "/"
index", temp_dir + "/index-preprocessed", "--storage-type", "
redis", "--redis-db", preprocess_redis_db_number];
66             run(cmd);
67             print("Input for index preprocessed.");
68         finally:
69             docker_rm(redis_container);
70
71     else:
72         print("Incorrect value for preprocess_storage_type");
73
74     for tgt in self.output():
75         with tgt.open("w") as f:
76             f.write("ok\n");

```

Preprocess is the first step of the workflow and is responsible for preparing the input data for subsequent processing by calling the *preprocess_input.py* script of OC Meta. The core logic of the task is parameterised by the *preprocess_storage_type* configuration option, selecting between two different backends for temporary identifier storage: a SPARQL triplestore (in this case, Apache Jena Fuseki), or a Redis key-value store. The preprocessing script uses this storage backend to perform lookups and consistency checks on the input identifiers. In case of an unsupported value for *preprocess_storage_type*, the task reports this misconfiguration via a simple diagnostic message.

When SPARQL is selected, the user-supplied SPARQL endpoint URL is parsed to extract the host, port and dataset path; this just performs basic validation, e.g. ensuring that a dataset name can be inferred from the endpoint path and warns the user if the endpoint host is not local, since the script exposes Fuseki only on

localhost. The task then launches a Docker container running Fuseki, publishing it on the appropriate port and binding the dataset name extracted from the endpoint. The *wait_for_port()* helper is used to block until the Fuseki service is network-ready. After it is made available, the preprocessing script is invoked twice via the *run()* helper; once for the Meta input directory, once for the Index input directory. Each call specifies the storage type as *sparql* and passes the configured endpoint. A *finally* block guarantees that the Fuseki container is stopped and removed.

When Redis is selected, an analogous sequence is followed; the task starts a Redis container via Dockers, waits for the Redis port to become reachable, and then calls the preprocessing script twice, separately for Meta and Index input. In this case, storage type is set to *redis* and the configured Redis database number is passed as an argument. The Redis container is then removed in a *finally* block.

4.1.4 Task 2 - Validation

Validation represents the second step in the workflow and is responsible for checking the syntactic and semantic correctness of the pre-processed input data, and if configured, applying corrective filtering.

The task begins by modifying the pre-processed Index data by removing columns that are deemed unnecessary by the *Validator* to the point of stopping the workflow. Using *pandas*, the task loads each CSV file, selects *citing* and *cited* columns and renames them to *citing_id* and *cited_id*.

Unlike other tasks of the pipeline that are centred on using scripts from either OC Meta or OC Index repositories, the validation is integrated using a programmatic invocation of the *Validator* class from the *oc.validator* package. As before, the validation process is performed independently for both Meta and Index.

In either case, each CSV file in the appropriate “pre-processed” directory is iterated over, then a snapshot of the validation directory is recorded, and existing JSON files with validation results are listed. The *Validator* object is then instantiated, having different options depending on the *validation_type* parameter; a standard validation, a validation querying a Meta endpoint, and a validation skipping identifier existence checks.

After calling *v.validate()*, a short delay is introduced to allow the validator to flush output to disk. Another snapshot of the validation directory is taken, and the newly created JSON file is identified by difference. This JSON report, among other things, specifies the row in which an error has occurred.

Once all validation have been performed, the elimination phase, controlled by the *validation_elimination* parameter, begins. Effectively, there are three modes; file-level elimination (*file*), line-level elimination (*line*), and no elimination in case the *validation_elimination* contains an invalid string.

4.1.5 Task 3 - DatabaseSwitchOn

DatabaseSwitchOn task prepares and initialises the database services required by the subsequent components of OC Meta and OC Index.

The task begins by ensuring that a Redis instance dedicated to Meta processing is running, by removing any previously running Redis container with *docker_rm()*.

This new Redis container is started through the *run()* helper, binding the configured host port to the container’s internal Redis port. The *wait_for_port* helper ensures that the Redis service is fully reachable at the network level before the workflow continues. Redis plays a role in identifier tracking for OC Meta and must be available before any provenance or metadata extraction occurs.

The next part of the task sets up the OpenLink Virtuoso triplestore, which is used as the storage backend for provenance information. Instead of directly calling Docker, the workflow delegates Virtuoso management to a set of specialised Python scripts provided by *virtuoso_utilities*. As such, complex Virtuoso configuration is isolated from the rest of the workflow and is reused, ensuring consistency with the OC Meta and OC Index tools.

The Virtuoso startup script accepts a large number of optional configuration parameters, which can be customised by the user through the workflow’s YAML configuration. These include the container name, HTTP and ISQL ports, data directory, database user credentials, container network, memory limits and data volume mappings. Each configured option is appended to the command dynamically, allowing the workflow to flexibly accommodate different deployment environments. After assembling the command with all relevant flags, the task invokes the script via *run()*.

Once Virtuoso is running, the next step is to rebuild its full-text index, which is required for efficient SPARQL text queries and provenance lookups. This is handled by the *rebuild_fulltext_index.py* script from the same utility suite. The workflow constructs the corresponding command, supplying the appropriate DBA password and any custom port or user options and runs it to regenerate indexing structures.

If provenance bulk load is enabled, the task finishes with invoking the *bulk_load.py* script, which recursively loads n-quads files from a user-specified directory into the Virtuoso triplestore, populating the PROV dataset.

4.1.6 Task 4 - OCMeta

OCMeta is responsible for orchestrating the execution of the OC Meta pipeline on the validated input data. The first part of the task focuses on the runtime construction of the *meta_config.yaml* file, which is the configuration file consumed directly by the OC Meta scripts. While the main workflow already uses a YAML file, its keys are named in a manner that is descriptive and convenient for the higher-level Luigi pipeline configuration (e.g. *meta_output_rdf_dir*). The OC Meta script expects a configuration file with a different internal structure and with keys according to its own schema. To bridge this mismatch, the *KEY_MAP* dictionary is used, mapping the configuration keys of the workflow, to those of OC Meta, including support for nested paths.

Instead of reading the main YAML file with a simple YAML loader, *ruamel.yaml* package is used in “round-trip” mode to preserve the exact representations of values; such as quoting style, leading zeroes, and other formatting details. This is particularly important for the supplier prefix, for which the default value of ‘060’ was incorrectly copied with several quotation marks. By copying the YAML nodes directly between documents such artefacts are avoided.

The transformation from the workflow configuration begins with loading the

workflow's YAML file into *src*, and a new *CommentedMap* named *dst* being created to hold the OC Meta configuration. For each pair of *src_path* → *dst_path*, the task navigates the nested structure of *src* to retrieve the corresponding value node, then recursively creates any necessary nested mappings in *dst* and inserts the node at the designated location. Errors encountered during this mapping process are accumulated in the *errors* list. If any mapping error occurs, the task raises a *ValueError*, preventing the pipeline from proceeding with an incomplete OC Meta configuration.

Once the mapping succeeds, the task serialises the constructed configuration to disk at the location specified by *meta_config_path*, again using *ruamel.yaml* in round-trip mode to preserve quoting and formatting. The resulting *meta_config.yaml* file is therefore a valid OC Meta configuration, derived consistently from the higher-level workflow configuration.

The second part of the task is responsible for actually running OC Meta. This is done via the generic *run()* helper, which calls the OC Meta entry point with the *-c* flag pointing to the freshly created *meta_config.yaml*. If OC Meta completes successfully, the extracted and processed RDF output is written to the directory specified in the configuration. However, if a *CalledProcessError* is raised, the task falls back to a recovery procedure, invoking a supplemental script. Its purpose is to upload any residual triples stored locally into the triplestore, ensuring that partial results are not lost if the main OC Meta run is interrupted.

After OC Meta (or its fallback script) finishes, the task shuts down the Meta-specific Redis container using *docker_rm()*, being consistent with the general approach of not leaving auxiliary services running around than necessary.

4.1.7 Task 5 - OCMetaCSV

OCMetaCsv is the second and final step of the Meta-processing part of the workflow. It has three main operations; running the validation of OC Meta (*oc_meta_val*), setting up a new Redis instance for *oc_meta_csv*, and finally running *oc_meta_csv* to reconstruct CSV output from RDF.

The task begins with the execution of a shell script to invoke *oc_meta_val*, a supplementary verification tool checking whether the CSV files produced by OC Meta are structurally and semantically correct according to OpenCitations' internal expectations. Currently, *oc_meta_val* outputs its findings only in the terminal window and does not produce machine-consumable output files. As such, although it is included in the pipeline for completeness, it does not influence any downstream logic. The workflow will continue regardless, even if it reports warnings and/or errors.

Next, a new instance of Redis is set up. Finally, the task invokes *oc_meta_csv*, which takes the RDF output generated during *OCMeta* and reconstructs the CSV files that represent the Meta dataset. A requirement of *oc_meta_csv* is that RDF files must have been generated during OC Meta. Otherwise, no RDF input would exist for reconstruction. Finally, the Redis instance used for this stage is closed.

4.1.8 Task 6 - Meta2Redis

Meta2Redis acts as the bridge between the Meta-processing and the Index-processing part of the pipeline. Its primary purpose is to load the cleaned and reconstructed Meta CSV files into a Redis database in the exact format expected by OC Index, which relies on Redis as an intermediate lookup structure to connect citation data to bibliographic entities.

The task begins by preparing a fresh Redis environment. Since the Redis instance used earlier in OC Meta and OCMetaCsv is removed at the end of those tasks to avoid contamination or unintended data reuse, *Meta2Redis* starts a new container from scratch.

Once Redis is ready, the task invokes the *meta2redis* script. The script is technically a part of the OC Index and is responsible for transforming the tabular metadata from OCMetaCSV into Redis-structured key-value pairs, which typically include normalised reference identifiers, bibliographic entity lookups, reverse lookups and cached entity metadata. This significantly speeds up OC Index runtime and ensures that cross-referenced citation data can be resolved efficiently even across large datasets.

4.1.9 Task 7 - OCIndexCNC

OCIndexCNC is responsible for executing the first of the three scripts that compose the *INDEX* part of the workflow. The task begins by constructing a configuration file in INI format required by the OC Index scripts. Similar to the case of OC Meta, OC Index codebase expects its own configuration, however, this time the file is an INI file with a specific section/key layout. To bridge this difference, *config.yaml* is read into a Python dictionary, and a *ConfigParser* instance is used to populate the INI configuration. Interpolation is explicitly disabled and *ini.optionxform = str* is used to preserve the case of option names.

A *KEY_MAP* dictionary defines how values from the YAML configuration are mapped into sections and keys in *config.ini*. Each entry in *KEY_MAP* associates a YAML key with a (*section, key*) pair in the INI file. The mapping covers several functional groups, e.g. [*identifier*] specifies which identifier schemes are used, [*cnc*] configures the Citation Network Construction module, including ORCID resolution, lookup behaviour, external services and database mappings for citations and bibliographic entities.

During configuration generation, the task iterates over each (*yaml_path, (section, key)*) in *KEY_MAP*. For each entry, it retrieves the corresponding value from the loaded YAML data using the *get_nested_yaml()* helper, which handles missing keys and nested structures. If a value is found, the task ensures that the target section exists in the *ConfigParser* instance and then assign the value to the appropriate key, always storing it as a string to match INI semantics. Missing keys are simply skipped, which allows the configuration file to remain flexible and avoids failing the pipeline because of non-essential parameters. After all mapped overrides have been applied, the task creates the output directory for the INI file if necessary and writes the fully populated configuration to disk using *ini.write()*. The resulting *config.ini* is then available for the OC Index scripts to consume.

Then, the task calls the first of the OC Index scripts, *cnc.py*, which constructs the citation network. It reads the validated Index CSV files, uses configuration from *config.ini* and Redis to resolve identifiers and enrich citation relations, and then constructs the citation network in a form suitable for indexing and provenance tracking. The `--processes` parameter allows parallelisation across multiple worker processes.

4.1.10 Task 8 - OCIndexCits2Redis

OCIndexCits2Redis is the second task in the *INDEX* part of the workflow. It is responsible only for running the *cits2redis.py* script, which loads the validated *INDEX* input into a database on a running REDIS instance.

4.1.11 Task 9 - OCIndexDump

OCIndexDump is the last of the tasks that run the *INDEX* part of the workflow. In this task, *dump_index.py* is executed. This script exports the content of Index into a set of dump files corresponding to the specified date. The dumps capture the state of the citation index in a portable format that can be published, archived, or further processed by other tools.

4.1.12 Task 10 - VirtuosoDump

VirtuosoDump task is responsible for exporting the final state of the provenance triplestore into a set of N-Quads dump files.

The *run()* method orchestrates the dump by invoking the *dump_quadstore.py* script from the *virtuoso_utilities* toolset. This script interacts with a running Dockerised OpenLink Virtuoso instance and performs a full dump of the quad store. The execution of this step is conditional; it only runs if *prov_virtuoso_dump* has been enabled in the configuration file. This allows the user to independently decide, whether provenance dumping should occur as part of the workflow.

The structure of the command constructed inside this task reflects the parameters required by the Virtuoso utilities. The script requires authentication credentials (DBA password and optionally a custom username), the output directory in which the N-Quads files will be written, and the parameters necessary to connect to the correct Docker container. The workflow supports additional customisation based on the values provided by *config.yaml*. After assembling the appropriate argument list, the task runs the command using the shared *run()* helper, ensuring consistent logging and error propagation across the workflow.

4.1.13 Task 11 - CleanUp

CleanUp is the final task of the workflow and is responsible for restoring the environment to a clean, reproducible state after all processing has completed. Its role is strictly operational: it ensures that no temporary files, intermediate products, or

leftover Docker containers persist between executions of the workflow, thereby preventing cross-run contamination and reducing the risk of subtle, state-based errors.

The first part of the *run()* method focuses on shutting down any remaining Docker containers. While most containers are explicitly removed in earlier tasks, the containers for Meta Redis and Virtuoso may still be running depending on the execution path. By invoking *docker_rm()* on both the Redis and Virtuoso containers, the task guarantees that no long-lived services remain active after the pipeline concludes.

Following container takedown, the task performs filesystem cleanup, beginning with the removal of the entire *temp_dir* containing all intermediate results generated across tasks such as *Preprocess*, *Validation* and *Meta2Redis*. Since none of these files are part of the final output, the entire directory is deleted using *shutil.rmtree*.

Then the output directory is pruned, as it contains a mix of final deliverables and runtime artefacts. Using the helper function *clean_directory_except()*, the task retains only a small whitelist of essential subdirectories (e.g. *ocmetacsv_output*). All other directories and files are removed. This allows the pipeline to present only the intended user-facing outputs.

Finally, the runtime helper files are deleted, which are produced during the execution of OpenCitations scripts; these include cache files, diagnostic logs, temporary CSVs, failed query logs or Windows helper batch files. These files are not meant to be included in the final dataset nor preserved between runs. The task removes them explicitly using *unlink(missing_ok = True)* to ensure that a missing file does not raise an exception.

4.2 Helper scripts

`trim_input.py`

The `trim_input()` helper script for trimming META input files serves as a preprocessing utility that adapts raw OpenCitations Meta dumps into a simplified and validator-compliant format suitable for controlled testing of the workflow. Its primary objective is not to transform the semantic content of the metadata, but rather to remove artefacts that would otherwise interfere with the preprocessing and validation stages, such as internal identifiers and inconsistent whitespace. This ensures that the generated test inputs resemble realistic data while remaining compatible with the expectations of the downstream tools.

The script performs a two-phase cleaning process. The first phase operates at the text level using regular expressions to eliminate OpenCitations Meta Identifiers (OMIDs), which are present in production dumps but should not appear in fresh ingestion inputs. OMIDs are removed both when they occur as standalone tokens and when embedded inside square-bracketed identifier groups. In the latter case, only the OMID component is discarded while preserving any remaining external identifiers. Additional substitutions normalise redundant whitespace and remove empty brackets, producing a syntactically cleaner intermediate file.

The second phase applies field-level normalisation using a tabular representation of the CSV data. Each cell value is stripped of leading and trailing whitespace, and column names are similarly cleaned. This step addresses subtle formatting issues, such as stray spaces, which would otherwise trigger validation errors (e.g., *extra_space*) in the `oc_validator` tool. By performing this pass after the textual cleanup, the script guarantees that all records conform strictly to the expected CSV structure.

This script functions as an auxiliary preparation step executed once prior to testing. It enables the reuse of publicly available Meta dumps as lightweight experimental datasets, reducing the need to construct synthetic inputs manually while ensuring that the files can be successfully processed by the preprocessing and validation components.

`generate_index_input.py`

The `generate_index_input.py` helper script responsible for generating synthetic INDEX input serves as a lightweight transformation layer between the output of the Meta stage and the input requirements of OC Index. Its purpose is to construct a consistent and self-contained citation dataset that reflects only entities actually produced during the workflow, thereby preventing references to non-existent records and eliminating validation mismatches during later processing stages.

At its core, the script scans all `output_*.csv` files generated as the output of the OC Meta processes and extracts identifiers exclusively from the `id` column. Since these fields may contain multiple identifiers, including internal OMIDs and external persistent identifiers, the function `first_non_omid_id()` selects the first token that is not prefixed with `omid:`. This ensures that only externally resolvable identifiers (e.g., DOI or OpenAlex IDs) are propagated into the generated INDEX input, matching

the expected format of the downstream tools.

After collecting identifiers, the script deterministically groups them into fixed-size batches. For each group, the first identifier is treated as the citing entity, while the remaining identifiers are treated as cited entities, producing a set of simple one-to-many citation relations. This grouping strategy guarantees reproducible and structurally valid citation graphs while keeping the dataset size manageable through configurable parameters such as *GROUP_SIZE* and *MAX_IDS*.

Finally, the generated citation pairs are written into a new CSV file containing only the citing and cited columns, directly matching the schema required by OC Index. Within the workflow, this script functions as a practical data preparation utility for testing and experimentation, enabling controlled generation of coherent INDEX input without relying on external or production-scale datasets.

4.3 Bugfixes

The testing of the workflow has shown a need to develop minor bugfixes for *virtuoso_utilities* and the *INDEX* scripts called by the Luigi tasks.

For *virtuoso_utilities*, the fix is just two lines long, and contains only an if-statement to check if the *dump_quadstore()* script used in the *VirtuosoDump* task is running on Windows with Virtuoso itself being launched inside a Docker container. This removed a bug, where the string containing the output directory for the dump inside the container had the main hard drive appended at the beginning.

The pull request containing the change is available at https://github.com/opencitations/virtuoso_utilities/pull/2.

For *INDEX*, the changes include adding a main call to four scripts called by the automated workflow, changing the hardcoded output value in *dump_index* to the directory used by the automated workflow, renaming the *scripts/redis* folder to avoid dependency naming issues with the *redis* Python package used by the scripts, removing unused/broken if checks in *cits2redis*, fixing reading unarchived CSV files by setting the reading to binary in *meta2redis*, and finally a fix for Windows-specific issue with setting the CSV field limit (related with conversion of Python *int* into C 32-bit *int*) in *cits2redis* and *meta2redis*.

The pull request containing the changes is available at <https://github.com/opencitations/index/pull/24>.

4.4 Repository

The public GitHub repository for the automated workflow is available at https://github.com/krzywonos/oc_automworkflow.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

In this chapter, the evaluation of the automatisisation will take place, divided into evaluating the implementation of the main flow, the implementation of alternate flows in the use case scenario, as well as the user requirements, all provided in Chapter 3; it will be followed by the evaluation of the risk planning made in Chapter 3.

5.1 Workflow analysis

5.1.1 Main flow analysis

```
Loaded config keys: blazegraph_container, blazegraph_image, fuseki_container, fuseki_image, index_cnc_br_ids, index_cnc_db_br, index_cnc_db_cifs, index_cnc_db_omid, index_cnc_db_ra, index_cnc_identifiers, index_cnc_lookup, index_cnc_orcid, index_cnc_processes, index_cnc_ra_ids, index_cnc_service_template_agent, index_cnc_service_template_baseurl, index_cnc_service_template_datasource, index_cnc_service_template_idbaseurl, index_cnc_service_template_identifier, index_cnc_service_template_parser, index_cnc_service_template_prefix, index_cnc_service_template_service, index_cnc_service_template_source, index_cnc_services, index_cnc_use_api, index_coci_identifier, index_coci_ocdump, index_coci_parser, index_coci_service, index_coci_source, index_croci_identifier, index_croci_ocdump, index_croci_parser, index_croci_service, index_croci_source, index_date, index_doci_identifier, index_doci_ocdump, index_doci_parser, index_doci_service, index_doci_source, index_dump_output, index_dumpindex_workers, index_identifier_doi, index_identifier_omid, index_identifier_pmid, index_index_agent, index_index_baseurl, index_index_datasource, index_index_db, index_index_idbaseurl, index_index_identifier, index_index_parser, index_index_prefix, index_index_service, index_index_source, index_index_validator, index_joci_source, index_logging_verbose, index_oroci_ocdump, index_oroci_parser, index_oroci_service, index_oroci_source, index_oroci_validator, index_poci_identifier, index_poci_ocdump, index_poci_parser, index_poci_service, index_poci_source, index_redis_batch_size, index_redis_host, index_redis_port, index_service, meta2redis_dir, meta_base_iri, meta_base_output_dir, meta_blazegraph_full_text_search, meta_cache_endpoint, meta_cache_update_endpoint, meta_config_path, meta_context_path, meta_default_dir, meta_dir_split_number, meta_fuseki_full_text_search, meta_generate_rdf_files, meta_graphdb_connector_name, meta_input_csv_dir, meta_items_per_file, meta_normalize_titles, meta_output_dir, meta_output_rdf_dir, meta_provenance_endpoints, meta_provenance_triplestore_url, meta_rdf_output_in_chunks, meta_redis_cache_db, meta_redis_container, meta_redis_db, meta_redis_host, meta_redis_port, meta_resp_agent, meta_silencer, meta_source, meta_supplier_prefix, meta_triplestore_url, meta_use_doi_api_services, meta_virtuoso_full_text_search, meta_workers_number, meta_zip_output_rdf, oc_index_cits2redis_dir, oc_index_cnc_dir, oc_index_config_dir, oc_index_dumpindex_dir, oc_meta_csv_dir, oc_meta_dir, oc_meta_dir_error, oc_meta_val_dir, oc_virtuoso_utilities_dir, preprocess_dir, preprocess_redis_db_number, preprocess_redis_port, preprocess_sparql_endpoint, preprocess_storage_type, prov_virtuoso_bulk_load, prov_virtuoso_bulk_load_dir, prov_virtuoso_custom, prov_virtuoso_data_dir, prov_virtuoso_dba_password, prov_virtuoso_dba_username, prov_virtuoso_detach, prov_virtuoso_dump, prov_virtuoso_dump_compression, prov_virtuoso_dump_dir, prov_virtuoso_dump_file_limit, prov_virtuoso_enable_write_permissions, prov_virtuoso_force_remove, prov_virtuoso_http_port, prov_virtuoso_isql_port, prov_virtuoso_memory, prov_virtuoso_mount_volume, prov_virtuoso_name, prov_virtuoso_network, prov_virtuoso_wait_ready, redis_container, redis_image, validation_elimination, validation_type
```

Figure 5.1: Results of loading the configuration

The main flow of the workflow begins with loading the configuration keys from the configuration file *config.yaml*. All keys are written to console in an alphabetical order.

```

DEBUG: Checking if Preprocess(param1=dir\temp\index-preprocessed\successtxt, param2=dir\temp\meta-preprocessed\successtxt) is complete
INFO: Informed scheduler that task Preprocess_dir_temp_index_p_dir_temp_meta_pr_eb2c208bde has status PENDING
DEBUG: Checking if Validation(param1=dir\temp\index-validated\successtxt, param2=dir\temp\meta-validated\successtxt) is complete
DEBUG: Checking if Preprocess(param1=dir\temp\index-preprocessed\successtxt, param2=dir\temp\meta-preprocessed\successtxt) is complete
INFO: Informed scheduler that task Validation_dir_temp_index_v_dir_temp_meta_va_cef77f277b has status PENDING
INFO: Informed scheduler that task Preprocess_dir_temp_index_p_dir_temp_meta_pr_eb2c208bde has status PENDING

```

Figure 5.2: Luigi processing the workflow steps

After loading the configuration, Luigi is initialised and begins to analyse all the steps of the workflow. Since the workflow is sequential and each step is configured to require the previous step to be finished, Luigi automatically creates a list of steps to be run in the order specified by the *requires()* functions of each step.

```

INFO: [pid 32208] Worker Worker(salt=3870632848, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=32208) running Preprocess(param1=dir\temp\index-preprocessed\successtxt, param2=dir\temp\meta-preprocessed\successtxt)
$ docker rm -f my-redis
$ docker run -d --name my-redis -p 6379:6379 redis:7-alpine
11755ee93d5229310df03eb300e6cb71b47f05d49e9ad51e8afaf8224958ee02
Redis ready at redis://localhost:6379
$ python ../oc_meta/oc_meta/run/meta/preprocess_input.py dir/input/meta dir/temp/meta-preprocessed --storage-type redis --redis-db 10
Found 10 CSV files to process
Using REDIS for ID existence checking
Processing CSV files: 100%|
| 10/10 [00:06<00:00, 1.56it/s]

Processing Report:
=====
Storage type used: REDIS
Total input files processed: 10
Total input rows: 30000
Rows discarded (duplicates): 0
Rows discarded (existing IDs): 0
Rows written to output: 30000

```

Figure 5.3: Running the *Preprocess* step

The first step of the workflow, *Preprocess*, runs a pre-validation script on the input CSV files of Meta and Index. As seen in figure 6.3, the preprocessing scripts returns a processing report with a brief summary of the work done.

```

100%|
| 3000/3000 [00:00<00:00, 80834.83it/s]
Validated META file no. 10: 9.csv → JSON: out_validate_meta_9.json, bad rows: 0
Validation elimination mode: LINE
Copied META CSV without changes: 0.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 1.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 2.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 3.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 4.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 5.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 6.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 7.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 8.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 9.csv

```

Figure 5.4: Validation

In the second step, *Validation*, The *Validator* validates each preprocessed file programatically. If there are no errors, a preprocessed file is copied in its entirety. If there is an error, the copying depends on the configuration; by default, the copying omits lines containing errors, but it can be changed to omit copying the entire file containing an error, or to stop the workflow.

```

Error executing ISQL command (Docker).
Command: ['docker', 'exec', 'virtuoso', 'isql', 'localhost:1111', 'dba', 'dba', 'exec=status();']
Return Code: 3
Stderr: *** Error S2801: [Virtuoso Driver]CL033: Connect failed to localhost:1111 = localhost:1111.
at line 0 of Top-Level:
Stdout: OpenLink Virtuoso Interactive SQL (Virtuoso)
Version 07.20.3239 as of Feb 13 2024
Type HELP; for help and EXIT; to exit.
Virtuoso is ready! (ISQL connection successful)
Enabling write permissions for 'nobody' and 'SPARQL' users...
Executing: DB.DBA.RDF_DEFAULT_USER_PERMS_SET('nobody', 7);
Successfully set permissions for 'nobody' user.
Executing: DB.DBA.USER_GRANT_ROLE('SPARQL', 'SPARQL_UPDATE');
Successfully granted SPARQL_UPDATE role to 'SPARQL' user.

Virtuoso launched successfully!
- Data Directory Host: C:\kucing\opencitations\oc_autoworkflow\virtuoso-data
- Data Directory Container: /opt/virtuoso-opensource/database
- Web interface: http://localhost:8888/conductor
- ISQL access (Host): isql localhost:1111 dba dba
- ISQL access (Inside container): isql localhost:1111 dba dba
- Container name: virtuoso

Additional mounted volumes:
- Host: C:\kucing\opencitations\oc_autoworkflow\dir\input\virtuoso -> Container: /input
- Host: C:\kucing\opencitations\oc_autoworkflow\dir\output\n-quads-dump -> Container: /output
DirsAllowed set in container via environment variable to: ../vad, ../virtuoso_input, /output, ., /usr/share/proj,
/input, /opt/virtuoso-opensource/database

```

Figure 5.5: Initialising Virtuoso

In the next step, *DatabaseSwitchOn*, instances of Redis and Virtuoso are initialised, the latter of which uses an OpenCitations' helper package *virtuoso_utilities*. Virtuoso does not initialised instantially, resulting in errors seen as above, but this is expected, and the script retries the initial connection to Virtuoso for a set amount of time. These errors, as well as a message showing the successful initialisation are shown in figure 6.5.

```

Bulk Load Summary:
- Files matching '*.nq.gz' registered and rdf_loader_run() executed in 0.37 seconds.
- No errors found in DB.DBA.load_list check and rdf_loader_run() succeeded.
-----
Caricamento bulk completato con successo per i file '*.nq.gz'.

```

Figure 5.6: Summary of bulk loading to Virtuoso

As an option, the user can configure the workflow to bulk load prepared N-Quads to Virtuoso. Figure 6.6 shows the summary of loading such files.

```

INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=
19688) running OCMeta(param=dir\output\meta\success.txt)
Wrote C:\kucing\opencitations\oc_autoworkflow\dir\temp\meta_config.yaml
$ python ../oc_meta/oc_meta/run/meta_process.py -c dir\temp\meta_config.yaml
Processing files: 0%| | 0/10 [00:00<?, ?it/s
jdir\temp\meta-validated\0.csv
Processing files: 10%| | 1/10 [00:57<08:37, 57.52s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\1.csv
Processing files: 20%| | 2/10 [02:25<10:04, 75.55s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\2.csv
Processing files: 30%| | 3/10 [03:22<07:49, 67.09s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\3.csv
Processing files: 40%| | 4/10 [04:23<06:28, 64.79s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\4.csv
Processing files: 50%| | 5/10 [05:26<05:19, 63.95s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\5.csv
Processing files: 60%| | 6/10 [06:22<04:04, 61.16s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\6.csv
Processing files: 70%| | 7/10 [07:22<03:02, 60.91s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\7.csv
Processing files: 80%| | 8/10 [08:23<02:01, 60.97s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\8.csv
Processing files: 90%| | 9/10 [09:24<01:00, 60.91s/it
jdir\temp\meta-validated\9.csv
Processing files: 100%| | 10/10 [10:23<00:00, 60.32s/it
Processing files: 100%| | 10/10 [10:23<00:00, 62.35s/it
]
Found 19025 files to process out of 19025 total files
Processing files: 100%| | 19025/19025 [19:04<00:00, 16.62it/s]
Found 19025 files to process out of 19025 total files
Processing files: 100%| | 19025/19025 [26:34<00:00, 11.93it/s]

Salvataggio cache su file...
Cache saved to ts_upload_cache.json
Cache salvato.

Salvataggio cache su file...
Cache saved to ts_upload_cache.json
Cache salvato.
$ docker rm -f redis
INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=
19688) done OCMeta(param=dir\output\meta\success.txt)

```

Figure 5.7: Result of *OCMeta*

The next step, *OCMeta*, loads data from the validated CSV files into Virtuoso. This is the longest step of the workflow. Cache is saved into a temporary JSON file.


```
[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:03,834 | INFO | oc.index : Uploading citations in RDF format to Redis
...
[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:03,876 | INFO | oc.index : Storing 8157 citations in Redis (<CITED>:[
<CITING-1>, ... <CITING-n>]) ...
[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:03,888 | INFO | oc.index : Done!
INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=
19688) done      OCIndexCits2Redis(param=dir\temp\index_cits2redis\success.txt)
```

Figure 5.11: Example output of *OCIndexCits2Redis*

OCIndexCits2Redis is the penultimate step calling an INDEX script. In this step the corresponding script reads the input INDEX files, and copies the found citations into a Redis database.

```
[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:04,130 | INFO | oc.index : Dumping all the citations in OpenCitations
Index ...
[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:04,130 | INFO | oc.index : ----- Configurations -----
ibase_url: https://w3id.org/oc/meta/
agent: https://w3id.org/oc/index/prov/pa/1
source: https://api.crossref.org/snapshots/monthly/2022/10
service: OpenCitations Index
identifier: omid
[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:04,130 | INFO | oc.index : ----- Process -----
CITED_BATCH_SIZE: 1500
CITED_PER_FILE: 10000
FILES_PER_ZIP: 1000
WORKERS: 1

[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:04,131 | INFO | oc.index : ----- Redis -----
REDIS_CITS_DB: 8
REDIS_METADATA_DB: 12

[MainProcess:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:04,131 | INFO | oc.index : Data will be stored in: 20251014
[Process-2:MainThread] 2026-02-14 13:36:05,890 | INFO | oc.index : Storing 3636 citations data of task 0...
INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=
19688) done      OCIndexDump(param=dir\output\index\success.txt)
```

Figure 5.12: *OCIndexDump* console output

OcIndexDump reads the information copied into the 5 Redis databases, and creates a dump in CSV, TTL and Scholix formats. Despite providing a date, which should correspond to a folder name where the output is supposed to be stored, the actual folder names are hardcoded; the final location of the folder is a constant and the subfolders are named after the year and month during which the dumping script have been called.

```
Step 1: Executing dump_nquads procedure...
Starting N-Quads dump using dump_nquads procedure...
Executing: dump_nquads('/output', 1, 100000000, 1);
OpenLink Virtuoso Interactive SQL (Virtuoso)
Version 07.20.3239 as of Feb 13 2024
Type HELP; for help and EXIT; to exit.
Connected to OpenLink Virtuoso
Driver: 07.20.3239 OpenLink Virtuoso ODBC Driver

Done. -- 15040 msec.
dump_nquads procedure completed successfully!

Dump completed successfully!
Total files created: 0
Output directory: /output
Output format: N-Quads (compressed)

Dump completed in 15.37 seconds
INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=
19688) done      VirtuosoDump(param=dir\output\n-quads-dump\success.txt)
```

Figure 5.13: Dumping N-Quads from Virtuoso

The penultimate step of the workflow contains an optional *virtuoso_utilities* script call that dumps the N-Quads containing the *PROV* provenance database.

The number of files created always displays 0, despite files being created as a result of running the script.

```
INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=19688) running Cleanup(param=cleanup.txt)
$ docker rm -f redis
$ docker rm -f virtuoso
INFO: [pid 19688] Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=19688) done Cleanup(param=cleanup.txt)
DEBUG: 1 running tasks, waiting for next task to finish
INFO: Informed scheduler that task Cleanup_cleanup_txt_a79571d2e9 has status DONE
```

Figure 5.14: Running the *CleanUp* step

Finally, the *CleanUp* step, which is the last in the workflow, turns off the running Docker instances of Redis and Virtuoso and removes the generated files that are not meant for final publication. The current version leaves the directory used by Virtuoso, this can be changed by uncommenting one line in this step.

```
DEBUG: Asking scheduler for work...
DEBUG: Done
DEBUG: There are no more tasks to run at this time
INFO: Worker Worker(salt=9278471102, workers=1, host=maszynka-tajemnic-hubiego, username=Hubi, pid=19688) was stopped. Shutting down Keep-Alive thread
INFO:
===== Luigi Execution Summary =====

Scheduled 11 tasks of which:
* 11 ran successfully:
- 1 Cleanup(param=cleanup.txt)
- 1 DatabaseSwitchOn(param=dir\temp\dbswitchon.txt)
- 1 Meta2Redis(param=dir\temp\meta2redis.txt)
- 1 OCIndexCNC(param=dir\temp\index_cnc\ocindex-data\success.txt)
- 1 OCIndexCits2Redis(param=dir\temp\index_cits2redis\success.txt)
...

This progress looks :) because there were no failed tasks or missing dependencies

===== Luigi Execution Summary =====
```

Figure 5.15: Luigi run summary

If there are no tasks left in the scheduler, the workflow concludes with a print from the Luigi Execution Summary, which shows the number and the list of tasks run successfully. Failed and pending tasks are printed in separate lists, if they occur.

Figure 5.16: Output directory

The output files generated and left after finishing the entire workflow are shown in figure 6.16. N-Quads dump from Virtuoso is put into one folder, META output in CSV and RDF formats are put into their own folder, and the INDEX dump in CSV, RDF and Scholix formats is put into its own separate folder. The *success.txt* files are Luigi's flags showing that their corresponding steps have been finished successfully.

In conclusion, as all steps run successfully, the main flow of the workflow can be considered as being implemented successfully.

5.1.2 Alternate flows analysis

In this subsection, the results of running the workflow with input and configuration set, so that the alternative flow can be tested will be examined.

```

ValueError: validation_type: 3 not in [0, 1, 2]
validation_elimination: 'test' not in ['file', 'line', 'workflow']
meta_rdf_output_in_chunks: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_workers_number: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_dir_split_number: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_items_per_file: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_generate_rdf_files: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_zip_output_rdf: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_normalize_titles: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
meta_use_doi_api_services: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_bulk_load: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_dump: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_dump_compression: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_custom: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_detach: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_wait_ready: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_enable_write_permissions: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'
prov_virtuoso_force_remove: invalid type/value 'test' (expected int) - invalid literal for int() with base 10: 'test'

```

Figure 5.17: Results of configuration validation

The configuration validation happens before the initialisation of the automated workflow. As such, if one of the variables that is checked for, as seen in figure 6.17, contains an invalid value or is of an invalid type, the workflow will not be initialised, and the errors are displayed correctly in the command line.

```

1 id,title,author,pub_date,venue,volume,issue,page,type,publisher,editor
2 ,GBIF Occurrence Download,Ocdownload Gbif.Org,2015,,,,,dataset,The Global B
3 testid,Occurrence Download,Ocdownload Gbif.Org,2019,,,,,dataset,The Global
4 test:id,Occurrence Download,Ocdownload Gbif.Org,2021,,,,,dataset,The Global

```

Figure 5.18: Testing values for input CSV file

For testing the *Validation* step, one of the input files has been slightly tweaked with to either delete or change an ID of a bibliographic entry into an unrecognised one.

```

100%|
| 3000/3000 [00:00<00:00, 80394.29it/s]
Validated META file no. 10: 9.csv → JSON: out_validate_meta_9.json, bad rows: 2
Validation elimination mode: LINE
Copied META CSV without changes: 0.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 1.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 2.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 3.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 4.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 5.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 6.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 7.csv
Copied META CSV without changes: 8.csv
Wrote META filtered CSV: 9.csv (removed 2 lines)

```

Figure 5.19: Results of validation by line

When running the *validation* step with the *validation_elimination* set by line, the workflow correctly finds and eliminates lines with invalid IDs. If an ID is empty, the line is not considered as invalid - this is the expected result of running *oc_validator*.

```
100%|
| 3000/3000 [00:00<00:00, 23068.36it/s]
Validated META file no. 10: 9.csv → JSON: out_validate_meta_9.json, bad rows: 2
Validation elimination mode: FILE
Copied META file: 0.csv
Copied META file: 1.csv
Copied META file: 2.csv
Copied META file: 3.csv
Copied META file: 4.csv
Copied META file: 5.csv
Copied META file: 6.csv
Copied META file: 7.csv
Copied META file: 8.csv
Skipping META file (has errors): 9.csv
```

Figure 5.20: Results of validation by file

When running the *validation* step with the *validation_elimination* set by file, the workflow correctly finds and avoids copying the files with invalid IDs.

5.1.3 Use case requirements analysis

User requirements with their priorities have been provided in section 3.1.3. Following is the table containing these user requirements, as well as the state of their implementation with additional explanation, where deemed necessary:

ID	Description	Status
UR-1	The application must implement the workflow automatization with all tools running in correct order in a single file.	Implemented
UR-2	The application must allow the user to specify the location of the input CSV documents.	Implemented - the location is also configurable
UR-3	The application must allow the user to specify the location of any output documents.	Implemented - the location is also configurable
UR-4	The application must have configurable options regarding validation, whether to stop the entire workflow upon failing to validate an entry, or to remove the entry and continue.	Implemented - the corresponding value is named <i>validation_elimination</i>
UR-5	The application must have appropriate error handling and logging; if a tool fails, a report stating what and why has failed, with a log for debugging purposes.	Implemented - error handling has been made a part of the workflow, OpenCitations' tools already have their own reports and logs for debugging purposes
UR-6	The application must correctly pass through and save all tool-specific flags.	Implemented
UR-7	The application should be implemented in Python, as is the rest of OpenCitations tools.	Implemented
UR-8	The application should prompt the user or require an explicit overwrite flag if output files already exist in the specified directory.	Not implemented - output files are generated with names or inside folders containing the date and time of their generation

ID	Description	Status
UR-9	The application should write logs to a text file.	Not implemented
UR-10	The application should notify the user upon the completion of the workflow.	Implemented - a system-specific pop-up notification is shown upon the completion of the workflow
UR-11	The application could show a summary report at the end of the execution (if it is possible according to the existing tool implementation)	Implemented - this is a default Luigi summary report
UR-12	The application could allow for simulating execution without producing any output.	Not implemented
UR-13	The application could support CLI arguments and configuration files.	Implemented - there is an additional CLI argument <code>--local-scheduler</code> to allow for running the workflow without starting the central Luigi scheduler
UR-14	The application will not have a graphical interface.	Skipped as intended
UR-15	The application will not modify tool logic, they are treated as working as is.	Minor bugfixes to <code>virtuoso_utilities</code> and <code>INDEX</code> scripts have been made in order to be able to test the entire workflow
UR-16	The application will not implement parallel execution of steps (which is also seemingly impossible with relation to the current workflow) to facilitate reading logs.	Skipped as intended

5.2 Risk planning analysis

The following table contains risks as identified in section 3.3.1:

ID	Type	Risk
R-T1	Technology	Loss of code or documentation
R-T2	Technology	Limitations of technology
R-T3	Technology	Unfamiliarity of technology
R-E1	Estimation	Underestimation of resources and time required

Risk planning involved identifying strategies aimed to manage the aforementioned risks. The strategies were initially categorised in three categories: avoidance, min-

imisation and contingency. Following are tables with the risk planning strategies, whether they were used and if so, in what manner:

ID	Category	Strategy	Use
R-T1	Avoidance	Use of a version control system with remote repository (e.g. Git with GitHub)	Used - a GitHub repository with code has been made and regularly updated
R-T1	Avoidance	Frequent commits with describing commit messages	Used - commits made were using descriptive commit messages containing changes that have been made since the previous commit.
R-T1	Avoidance	Storing copies of the thesis document and code in cloud storage	Used - periodic backups of code and the thesis document have been made to multiple external hard drives and cloud drives.
R-T1	Minimisation	Periodic manual backups	Used - periodic backups of code and the thesis document have been made to multiple external hard drives and cloud drives.
R-T1	Minimisation	Partial separation of raw data, generated output and source code	Used - the script has been placed in the main directory, while data used as input has been placed in a subfolder named <i>input</i> . Generated data is put into other subfolders named <i>temp</i> and <i>output</i> .
R-T1	Minimisation	Clear directory structure to avoid accidental deletion	Used - the script has been placed in the main directory, while data used as input has been placed in a subfolder named <i>input</i> . Generated data is put into other subfolders.

ID	Category	Strategy	Use
R-T1	Contingency	Restoration of the repository to a previous commit	Not used
R-T1	Contingency	Recloning the remote repository onto a new machine	Not used
R-T1	Contingency	Regeneration of the intermediate files using the reproducible workflow	Not used

ID	Category	Strategy	Use
R-T2	Avoidance	Analysing possible workflow managers before implementation	Used - the analysis has been made a part of the final thesis document as section 4.2.
R-T2	Avoidance	Choosing technologies with active documentation and support	Used - the final choice of Luigi has been made with this as one of the reasons.
R-T2	Avoidance	Selecting Docker-based deployment where applicable to isolate environments	Used - this turned out to not be a risk planning method, but a choice made by the developers of OpenCitations' tools.
R-T2	Contingency	Replacing individual components	Not used
R-T2	Contingency	Limiting scope to supported features while documenting constraints	Used - See chapter 7, sections 7.1 and 7.2.

ID	Category	Strategy	Use
R-T3	Avoidance	Preliminary experimentation with new technologies before integrating them into the workflow	Not used
R-T3	Avoidance	Reading documentation and studying example configurations	Used - example configurations of Luigi and OpenCitations tools have been examined before the start of the development process
R-T3	Avoidance	Starting with a proof-of-concept pipeline before expanding it further to include tools	Used - a proof-of-concept pipeline has been the starting point of the automated workflow
R-T3	Minimisation	Developing the workflow incrementally	Used - the workflow has been developed in a step-by-step basis
R-T3	Minimisation	Use of logging and explicit error handling	Used - when appropriate, e.g. loading the configuration
R-T3	Minimisation	Debugging via container inspection	Used - specifically for configuration of <i>Virtuoso</i> and debugging the <i>INDEX</i> tools
R-T3	Contingency	Consulting documentation and issue trackers	Used - for Luigi pipeline development
R-T3	Contingency	Pinning versions of dependencies to avoid unexpected behavioural changes	Used - specifically for <i>virtuoso_utilities</i> version 1.4.0.

ID	Category	Strategy	Use
R-E1	Avoidance	Breaking down the project into clearly defined phases	Used
R-E1	Avoidance	Identifying dependencies early	Used - e.g. with the selection of the automation framework
R-E1	Avoidance	Including buffer time in planning	Used
R-E1	Minimisation	Developing the workflow incrementally	Used - the workflow has been developed in a step-by-step basis
R-E1	Minimisation	Preparing a small example input dataset for testing purposes	Used - this has been described in section 5.2.
R-E1	Minimisation	Reusing existing OpenCitations' utilities where possible	Used - e.g. <i>virtuoso_utilities</i>
R-E1	Contingency	Reducing input dataset size for evaluation	Used - for testing purposes, 30000 lines have been taken from the latest OpenCitations Meta dump.
R-E1	Contingency	Narrowing evaluation scope to workflow-level validation	Used - work on the OpenCitations scripts has not been planned, and the bugfixes made have been necessary in order to test the workflow
R-E1	Contingency	Prioritising core functionality over optional features	Used - explained in section 6.1.3.
R-E1	Contingency	Freezing feature development to grant time for documentation	Used - the workflow has been finalised some time before the final deadline to allow work on the documentation.

No additional strategies for avoidance, minimisation and contingency of risks were used during the development, and as such, the risk planning can be categorised as having been made properly and duly.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this dissertation, I have introduced the OpenCitations project and the collections it generates, the existing workflow of OpenCitations, its' tools and services, and the underlying theory and generation process of OpenCitations Meta and OpenCitations Index, i.e. OpenCitations' two main collections. Additionally, I made research into open research information providers related to OpenCitations, with a brief look for each's data ingestion pipeline; this was followed by an examination of some of the existing open-source pipeline automation frameworks. An automated version of the existing OpenCitations workflow was the main practical result of the thesis, with minor bugfixes for existing OpenCitations' tools developed during the development and testing process. Finally, the automated workflow has been evaluated.

The proposed workflow contributes to OpenCitations by introducing an integrated and reproducible execution layer over the existing toolchain used for Meta and Index generation. It formalises dependencies, configuration handling and execution order, thereby reducing manual intervention and time spent on and between running the tools and improving robustness during repeated or long-running executions by preventing invalid executions, avoiding partial states and ensuring repeatability of executions.

In the rest of the concluding chapter of the thesis, I will present the existing limitations of the project. The chapter will continue with a list of possible extensions for the implementation, a short analysis of aims and objectives introduced in the first chapter and conclude with a self-evaluation.

6.1 Limitations

The main limitation of the project is its partial (but still a major) coverage of the existing OpenCitations' data generation workflow. While the existing automatisations have been fully covered, the workflow does not cover all existing auxiliary tools and optional scripts, focusing on the core generation of Meta and Index databases. Most of the scripts were invoked as is, without a specific research into what they actually do.

The workflow depends entirely on external repositories and scripts, and as such, changes in those projects may introduce incompatibilities. For example, *virtuoso_utilities*, which worked as intended in the version 1.4.0, but which I cannot currently get to run correctly on my machine, since it is developed in mind with the production environment on Linux.

The evaluation provided in the previous chapter focuses on just the functional correctness. Since generation is handled at the level of scripts provided by the OpenCitations' tools, no insight into the reproducibility of the results can be made. Additionally, no stress testing at production scale has been made. Finally, I have not made any benchmarking of execution time across different environments and hardware configurations.

There were some environment assumptions made during the development, namely assuming Docker availability, which is currently used in the OpenCitations' workflow. Additionally, the workflow has been developed and tested only on a specific OS (Windows), so while there are checks and minor differences, e.g. in producing an appropriate pop-up notification upon finishing the workflow based on the operating system used, no testing has been made to ensure that these are functionally correct (e.g. I do not own a MacOS machine).

As mentioned previously, testing was not performed at production scale, and evaluation has used reduced test datasets. For controlled testing, I have used synthetic citation generation for the input CSV of INDEX. This means that the results may not necessarily reflect full-scale production runs.

Finally, the automated workflow is based on a sequential execution model, and it runs with just a single worker process. Parallel execution is not exploited, even if it is so by design of the original workflow.

6.2 Possible extensions

The most important possible extension would be to implement the missing parts of the existing OpenCitations' workflow, that is the procurement of input data using APIs and uploading the output files to appropriate repositories (such as Figshare and Zenodo).

The automated workflow could be provided as a single Docker Compose setup, removing existing dependency on local environment configuration.

An extension including support for Continuous Integration could be made. In this way, compatibility with new releases of OpenCitations' releases could be made, as well as automatic validation test on configuration changes.

Finally, there could be a formal evaluation framework, with defined KPIs such as execution time. There could also be an additional evaluation made, comparing time spent on manual execution of the tools against the automated workflow. Ideally, this would be done at production scale.

6.3 Analysis of aims and objectives

The following is a list of aims and objectives from the Introduction chapter of the thesis, joined with an analysis on whether or not I was able to fulfil them:

1. Research OpenCitations

Conducting research on OpenCitations to gain understanding on the system that will be automatised. This includes the preprocessing (extracting citations and metadata), OpenCitations Meta (curation of metadata, allocation of identifiers, metadata and provenance of data production), and OpenCitations Index (conversion of citations, production of citation and provenance data).

This objective was achieved, and is present in this document as a section of the Implementation Review chapter. Not every paper released on OpenCitations has been relevant to the topic, and as such, some aspects (e.g. OpenCitations' programming interface) were purposefully omitted. Additional research, unexpected before starting the work on the thesis, went into the OpenCitations' *Validator*.

2. Research other attempts at developing open bibliographic data

Conducting research on related works, i.e. other existing attempts at developing open-source bibliographic citation projects, such as (but possibly not limited to) OpenAIRE, OpenAlex and WikiCite. The goal of this objective is to provide a deeper look and understanding of the open science community and the need to provide free options for providing data relating to bibliographic citations.

This objective was achieved and is present in this document as its own chapter. Ten related works have been identified, which is not a conclusive list, and two of them are not active. Microsoft Semantic Scholar, which is a major related work has been completely omitted, since its databases have been taken over and are in active development by OpenAlex.

3. Research potential tools

Conducting research on tools that may be used for the implementation of the automatization process of OpenCitations. While the main aim of the project is to provide a process that will be compliant with the CC0 licence, additional methods will be looked into as well, to provide a more "state-of-the-art" approach if applicable.

This objective was achieved and is present in this document as a section of the Literature review chapter. Four tools for automatization workflow have been examined, which is not an exhaustive list; however this number should prove to be satisfactory in order to provide an outline of existing free tools that can be used in this manner.

4. Implement the automatization

Developing the automatization process of creating the OpenCitations database.

This objective was achieved and is described in the Implementation chapter. The final implementation of the workflow differs slightly from what was

planned, but nevertheless the existing automatisisation needs have been successfully addressed.

5. Evaluate the automatization

Evaluating the accomplishment of user requirements, running the workflow locally (i.e. on my personal computer) and evaluating the correctness of main and alternative workflows.

This objective was achieved and is described in the Evaluation chapter. This has been augmented by the evaluation of risk planning as a further insight into the self-evaluation of project management.

Bibliography

- Airflow 2025a, *Github apache/airflow*, <https://github.com/apache/airflow>
- Airflow 2025b, *What is AirFlow? - Airflow 3.0.3 Documentation*, <https://airflow.apache.org/docs/apache-airflow/stable/index.html>
- Auer S., et al., 2020, *Improving access to scientific literature with knowledge graphs*, *Bibliothek Forschung und Praxis*, 44, 516
- Barcelona Declaration 2024, *Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.10958522, <https://barcelona-declaration.org/downloads/BarcelonaDeclaration.pdf>
- Bik A., et al., 2012, *Age Spread in W3 Main*, *ApJ*, 744, 87
- BioTea 2012, *BioTea dataset (vr. July 2012)*, <https://zenodo.org/records/376814>
- BioTea 2025d, *biotea organisation on GitHub*, <https://github.com/biotea>
- BioTea 2025b, *Biotea release August 2017*, <https://biotea.github.io/datasets/201708>
- BioTea 2025c, *Biotea release February 2019*, <https://biotea.github.io/datasets/201902>
- BioTea 2025a, *BioTea release July 2012*, <https://biotea.github.io/datasets/201207>
- BioTea 2025e, *Software*, <https://biotea.github.io/software/>
- Celery 2025a, *Github celery/celery*, <https://github.com/celery/celery>
- Celery 2025b, *Introduction to Celery - Celery 5.5.3 documentation*, <https://docs.celeryq.dev/en/stable/getting-started/introduction.html>
- Celery 2025c, *Introduction to Celery - Celery 5.5.3 documentation*, <https://docs.celeryq.dev/en/v5.5.3/getting-started/next-steps.html>
- Crossref 2025, *Metadata Retrieval*, <https://www.crossref.org/services/metadata-retrieval>
- Daquino M., et al., 2020, *The OpenCitations Data Model. The Semantic Web, ISWC 2020*, 12507, 447

- Fortunato S., et al., 2018, *Science of science*, [Science Magazine](#), 6379
- Franchuk N., 2023, *Tekhnolohija Vykorystannja vidkrytoho ukraïnskoho indeksu cytovan dlja ocinjuvannja rezultatyvnosti pedahohichnykh doslidzhen*, [Osvita. Innovatika. Praktika](#), 5, 95
- Fricke S., 2018, *Semantic Scholar*, [Journal of the Medical Library Association](#), 106, 145
- Garcia A., Lopez F., Garcia L., Giraldo O., Bucheli V., Dumontier M., 2018, *Biotea: Semantics for Pubmed Central*, [PeerJ](#), 6
- Gentile A., Nuzzolese A., 2016a, *cLODg*, <https://github.com/AnLiGentile/cLODg>
- Gentile A., Nuzzolese A., 2016b, *cLODg - Conference Linked Open Data Generator*, https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1486/paper_85.pdf
- Gilligan S., 2021, *How To Build a Data Processing Pipeline Using Luigi in Python on Ubuntu 20.04*, <https://www.digitalocean.com/community/tutorials/how-to-build-a-data-processing-pipeline-using-luigi-in-python-on-ubuntu-20-04>
- Hammond T., Pasin M., Theodoridis E., 2017, *Data integration and disintegration: Managing Springer Nature SciGraph with SHACL and OWL*, ISWC (Posters, Demos Industry Tracks), 1963
- Heibi I., Moretti A., Peroni S., Soricetti M., 2024, *The OpenCitations Index: Description of a database providing open citation data*, *Scientometrics*, 129, 7923
- Kinney R. e. a., 2025, *The Semantic Scholar Open Data Platform*, arXiv
- Kurtz S., 2005, *Hypercompact HII regions*, [IAU Symp.](#), 1, 111
- Lammey R., 2020, *Using the Crossref REST API (with Open Ukrainian Citation Index)*, doi:10.64000/r5exe-m8m40, <https://www.crossref.org/blog/using-the-crossref-rest-api-with-open-ukrainian-citation-index/>
- Manghi P., Manola N., Horstmann W., Peters D., 2010, *An infrastructure for managing EC funded research output - The OpenAIRE project*, *Grey Journal (TGJ)*, 6
- Manghi P., et al., 2022, *OpenAIRE Research Graph Dataset*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.3516917
- Massari A., Mariani F., Heibi I., Peroni S., Shotton D., 2024, *OpenCitations Meta*, [Quantitative Science Studies](#), 5, 50
- Mora-Cantalops M., Sánchez-Alonso S., García-Barriocanal E., 2019, *A systematic literature review on Wikidata*, [Data Technologies and Applications](#), 53, 250
- Moreau L., Missier P., 2013, *PROV-DM: The PROV data model.*, <http://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

Nuzzolese A. G., Gentile A. L., Presutti V., Gangemi A., 2016, *Semantic web conference ontology—A refactoring solution*, [European Semantic Web Conference](#), pp 84–87

ORKG 2025a, *Open Research Knowledge Graph*, <http://orkg.org>

ORKG 2025b, *Open Research Knowledge Graph - Data access*, <http://orkg.org/data>

ORKG 2025c, *Open Research Knowledge Graph - Licence*, <http://orkg.org/page/license>

ORKG 2025d, *Tools overview*, <https://orkg.org/tools>

OUCI 2025, *OUCI*, <https://ouci.dntb.gov.ua/en/about/>

OpenAIRE 2025a, *Documentation - Downloads*, <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/category/downloads>

OpenAIRE 2025c, *Documentation - License*, <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/license>

OpenAIRE 2025d, *Documentation - Overview*, <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/>

OpenAIRE 2025b, *OpenAIRE - Find and search research*, <https://explore.openaire.eu/>

OpenAIRE 2025e, *OpenAIRE Research Graph - Documentation*, https://support.openaire.eu/projects/docs/wiki/OpenAIRE_Research_Graph

OpenAlex 2025d, *Data ingest pipeline*, <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/25271311639063-Data-ingest-pipeline>

OpenAlex 2025c, *How does OpenAlex work?*, <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/28932712154391-How-does-OpenAlex-work>

OpenAlex 2025e, *OpenAlex pipeline*, <https://unpaywall-metabase.herokuapp.com/public/dashboard/8e114521-b74b-4e6c-bba8-3a8fc573fb64>

OpenAlex 2025a, *OpenAlex: The open catalog to the global research system*, <https://openalex.org>

OpenAlex 2025b, *Pricing*, <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/24397762024087-Pricing>

OpenCitations 2023, *OpenCitations Index CSV dataset of all the citation data*, doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.24356626.v6, https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/OpenCitations_Index_CSV_dataset_of_all_the_citation_data/24356626

OpenCitations 2025b, *OpenCitations Download page*, <https://download.opencitations.net/>

- OpenCitations 2025a, *OpenCitations Meta CSV dataset of all bibliographic metadata*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.15625651, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15625651>
- Pasin M., 2025, *SciGraph 2017-2023*, <https://www.michelepasin.org/blog/2023/02/03/rip-scigraph/index.html>
- Peroni S., Rizzetto E., 2025, *A Tool for Validating and Monitoring Bibliographic Data in Open Research Information Systems: The OpenCitations Collections*, Proceedings of the 21st Conference on Information and Research science Connecting to Digital and Library science. Udine, Italy, February 20-21, 2025 (Vol. 3937). CEUR-WS.org
- Peroni S., Shotton D., 2018, *Open Citation: Definition.*, doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.6683855
- Peroni S., Shotton D., 2019, *Open Citation Identifier: Definition.*, doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.7127816
- Peroni S., Shotton D., 2020, *OpenCitations, an infrastructure organization for open scholarship*, *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1, 428
- Peroni S., Shotton D., Vitali F., 2016, *A document-inspired way for tracking changes of RDF data—The case of the OpenCitations Corpus*, Detection, Representation and Management of Concept Drift in Linked Open Data, 1799, 26
- Prefect 2025a, *Github PrefectHQ/prefect*, <https://github.com/PrefectHQ/prefect>
- Prefect 2025b, *Introduction - Prefect*, <https://docs.prefect.io/v3/get-started>
- Prefect 2025c, *Quickstart - Prefect*, <https://docs.prefect.io/v3/get-started/quickstart>
- Priem J., Piwowar H. A., Orr R., 2022, *OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts*, *arXiv*
- ScholarlyData 2025, *Welcome to scholarlydata.org*, <https://scholarlydata.org/>
- Scholia 2025, *Statistics*, <https://scholia.toolforge.org/statistics>
- SemanticScholar 2025c, *License agreement*, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/product/api/license>
- SemanticScholar 2025a, *Semantic Scholar — AI-Powered Research Tool*, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>
- SemanticScholar 2025b, *Semantic Scholar Academic Graph API*, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/product/api>
- Shotton D., 2013, *Linked data 101*, <https://semanticpublishing.wordpress.com/2013/03/01/linked-data-101/>

- Sinha A., Shen Z., Song Y., Ma H., Eide D., Hsu B., Wang K., 2015, *An overview of Microsoft Academic Service (MAS) and applications*, *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on World Wide Web*, pp 243–246
- Spotify 2025, *Github spotify/luigi*, <https://github.com/spotify/luigi>
- Taraborelli D., 2016, *WikiCite 2016. Berlin, Germany*, https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:WikiCite_2016_slidedeck.pdf
- Tay A., Martín-Martín A., Hug S. E., 2021, *Goodbye, Microsoft Academic – hello, open research infrastructure? Impact of Social Sciences Blog*, <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/id/eprint/111325>
- WikiData 2025b, *Data import guide*, https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Data_Import_Guide
- WikiData 2025a, *Database download*, https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Database_download
- WikiData 2025c, *WikiCite*, <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiCite>
- iCite 2025b, *Data handling*, <https://support.icite.nih.gov/hc/en-us/articles/8946913676059-Data-Handling>
- iCite 2025a, *iCite — Analysis*, <https://icite.od.nih.gov/analysis>